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**Homecoming to Karabakh: From Ghost Towns to Smart Towns through the Eyes of
Returning IDPs.**

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ABSTRACT

This dissertation examines the experiences of Azerbaijani citizens who were internally displaced from the Karabakh region and returned to their homeland, and the impact of this process on their memory, identity, and sense of place. At the same time, this work encompasses not only the moment of return but also all the processes experienced from the beginning of the period of internal displacement to the present day, including the life of displacement, losses, expectations, and ultimately, the experience of return. It should be especially emphasized that such cases are rare, since in very few cases people from the same generation could return to the lands from which they were displaced. In this regard, the experience covered in this dissertation and its analysis are extremely valuable and of particular importance. The research examines the anthropological aspects of the concepts of home, place, and return home, contextualizes the war, displacements and returns from Karabakh historically, examines and looks closely at the biographical experiences of IDPs - the emotional and social changes they experience during displacement, the years of being IDPs and their return, and their desire to return. In the study, which is based on ethnographic and semi-structured, biographical interviews were conducted with 12 individuals formerly displaced from Karabakh, and with one new settler, a member of Karabakh University. The results of the study showed that returning to Karabakh is not only a change of physical space, but also a process of rebuilding individual and collective memory, restoring social relations, and searching for identity. The study reveals the process of reshaping the concept of home and place in the socio-cultural and historical context of Karabakh. It further analyzes the emotional and psychological effects of this return against the background of individual stories of formerly displaced individuals.

Keywords: home, place, IDP, Karabakh, homecoming, collective memory, identity, smart villages

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THE LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADA – Azerbaijan Diplomatic Academy

APFP – Azerbaijan Popular Front Party

ARMSTAT – Statistical Committee of the Republic of Armenia

CEPA – Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement

CIS – Commonwealth of Independent States

CSTO – Collective Security Treaty Organization

EU – European Union

FGD – Focus Group Discussion

IASFM – International Association for the Study of Forced Migration

IDMC – Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre

IDP – Internally Displaced Person

KGB – Komitet Gosudarstvennoy Bezopasnosti (Committee for State Security in English)

NATO – North Atlantic Treaty Organization

NGO – Non-Governmental Organization

NRC – Norwegian Refugee Council

OSCE – Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe

PTSD – Post Traumatic Stress Disorder

UNHCR – United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

UNESCO – United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization

USA – United States of America

USSR – Union of Soviet Socialist Republics

WHO – World Health Organization

WW II – World War II

INTRODUCTION

The concept of home is one of the most valuable and influential feelings in human life. Even if a person sometimes lives in different geographies and changes many houses in his life, there is always a sense of attachment to the place where he was born, raised, or where he attached his values. Especially for people who are displaced from their homeland, “home” is not only a physical space consisting of four walls, but also a spiritual value that carries the burden of memory, remembrance, and identity. For this reason, the process of returning to a region like Karabakh, which has been under occupation for many years and whose inhabitants have become internally displaced persons, does not only have a geographical and physical meaning. This process also encompasses emotional and psychological aspects such as the reconstruction of individual, social, and collective memory, the renewal of identities, and the restoration of lost social relationships.

The main purpose of this dissertation is to examine the process of returning to one's native land through the eyes of internally displaced persons returning to Karabakh and to study the impact of this return on their identities, collective memories, and spatial concepts. For people who have lived as internally displaced persons for many years, the fact that the homeland they return to is no longer the same as before, and that it has changed physically and socially, raises various questions and contradictions in their memory and emotional world. In this regard, in addition to the physical boundaries of space, its emotional and cultural meaning is also of great importance. Thus, returnees are not only searching for their homes and lands, but also for their past and lost roots.

During the research, the feelings experienced by the internally displaced persons during the return process, the new social and spatial order they encountered, as well as their attitudes towards this change, were examined interviews. In addition, theoretical approaches to the concept of home and return home in the global and Azerbaijani contexts were analyzed. The Karabakh issue was not only a political and military problem but also played a decisive role in the formation of Azerbaijan's national identity and collective memory. The return to Karabakh can be assessed as the revival of this memory and the beginning of a new stage in the lives of internally displaced persons. Since long historical facts are mentioned when discussing this conflict with a long history, the background part is given a little longer. Because the losses given as each historical fact and figure

written down help to understand the past of the geography and the people before and after their displacement.

The interviews focused on the respondents' personal life experiences, their sense of home, their memories of the place, and the social and emotional situations they encountered during the return process. In addition, the physical and social changes of the place were documented. This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the effects of the return process to Karabakh on human life and identity. At the same time, during the transcription and recording of the interviews, artificial intelligence-powered tools were used to capture and capture the emotional tone and expressions of the participants as accurately as possible. This technology was not used to analyze emotions in real time during the interviews, but rather to translate and transcribe the interviews into written material after the interviews. This approach was used to ensure that the feelings and emotional tone expressed during the interviews were not lost in the recording process.

The dissertation also aims to analyze how the concepts of “home”, “homeland”, “space”, and “memory” are formed and changed within the framework of anthropological theory to understand the emotional and social changes that returning home brings to human life. Thus, this work not only presents the stories of those who returned to Karabakh but also reveals the value of the concepts of home and space in the world of people’s identity and memory.

1. CONCEPTS OF HOME AND AZERBAIJANI UNDERSTANDING

Under which circumstances do people become homesick, and what does it mean to groups and individuals in different contexts to be homesick? Many researchers from various disciplines have asked themselves this question (cf. Winning, 1990; Duyvendak, 2011; Feng & Breitung, 2018). In this dissertation, I will also research the histories of displacement and recent resettlement in Karabakh, Azerbaijan, from an anthropological perspective. Sometimes, we experience a place without identifying it, either as the specificity of the notion of home or as the description of our sentiments. Until we lose it. Even if we change places and houses, the term "home" is valid for many of us. We especially start to feel this feeling more after we move away from there. For many of us, the home we feel familiar with and attached to is the house we currently live in. For some of us, it is a place we visit occasionally. However, unfortunately, many individuals today have no home to return to. Lives, wars, and political factors have taken away this feeling of a place that feels like home. The definition of home varies depending on everyone's perspective. While one person may describe a home as just four walls, for some, another may call the same house a home, imbued with meanings. It is an immovable entity full of memories, where emotions accumulate. It is a place that is difficult to describe and identify. Just as the concept of home varies from person to person, the feeling of longing for home also varies from person to person. However, the feeling of longing naturally connects us as an emotion. When we consider the word "homesick" as a word that unites these feelings (feeling at home, or missing the home) under itself, we feel that many people share this feeling, and we realize that we are not alone.

Traditionally, the sense of "being at home" has been associated with a specific physical space, family, and familiarity. However, globalization and increased mobility have shown that this familiarity component alone is not enough. While some have adopted a nomadic lifestyle, others seek the familiarity and sense of belonging of their old homes. Mobile individuals often use a "mobile home strategy" to recreate their old surroundings in new environments, bring products from their homeland, and thus adapt to new places. This is also related to class differences. The spatial advantage of the wealthy and mobile class can create social tensions by creating threats for the disadvantaged. The sense of "being at home" is a complex emotional and social concept that extends not only to personal space, but also to neighborhood, homeland, workplace, and wider

social spaces. It encompasses feelings of familiarity, security, intimacy, and belonging. This concept can be evaluated from both universalist and particularist perspectives. The universalist approach emphasizes that people continue to search for connections and identity with specific places, despite increasing mobility and globalization. The particularist approach also evaluates the attachment to local places as a defensive reaction against globalization. When looking at the historical context, sociologists have relegated local ties to the background, emphasizing cosmopolitan ideals and shifting identities. Mobility and social mobility have become a value, especially in mobile societies like the United States. Gender dynamics have also influenced this process; while men were previously expected to be free to move and women to be deeply attached, the feminist movement has changed these perceptions. Economic instability, the housing crisis, and changes in gender roles have created a crisis in the concept of “home.” Some people now report that they feel more comfortable in their work environment than at home. Moreover, issues of safety and anxiety accompany themes of belonging at both the individual and national levels. Thus, when approaching the issue of belonging, it is important to understand the complex relationship between mobility, identity, and social values, considering historical, social, and cultural contexts (Duyvendak, 2011).

Duyvendak’s (2011) account of “being at home” from both universalist and particularist perspectives provides an important theoretical foundation for my research. For me, the feeling of “being at home” is not just a return to a geographical or physical place, but also an identity that is reconstructed within emotional, social, and political processes. For returning IDPs, the concept of “home” is not only about nostalgia, but also about the restoration of a new life, security. As Duyvendak suggests, everyone can experience the feeling of “being at home” in different places and situations, but my fieldwork has shown that this part can differ significantly according to gender, generation, and the circumstances of displacement.

The experience of homesickness also raises the question of what it means to be “not at home.” In order to better understand homesickness on an individual basis, we need a clearer sense of home. The most common question about home to a person living away from home is “Where do you come from?” The question is asked. When people ask this question, they admit that there is a big difference between living somewhere and coming from somewhere. In my daily life as a foreign student, the question I hear most when meeting people is “Where are you from?”. This question

can make you feel proud of a place you miss and feel attached to, but it can also be used to make you feel less at home and fit in the place you are making a home in, at least a temporary one. Where a person comes from is his home: While we can say that home is the end point, we can also say that it is the starting point. As we grow older and open up to the wider world, this sense of home seems to expand within us. The interior of the house is the place where one can kick back, breathe easily as shoes give way to slippers, and find the right space to just be oneself. So, this classic "Where do you come from?". As the answer to the question requires a response that includes awareness of where we belong, where we feel physically, spatially, temporally, and socially "in tune" with the details of the life world (Winning, 1990).

Winning (1990) notes that the question "Where are you from?" requires a person to express where they belong, where they feel comfortable and appropriate. Based on this idea, I want to show that this question sometimes creates a sense of nostalgia and longing for internally displaced people, but sometimes it also causes anxiety and uncertainty. Because for them, the concept of "home" is connected with both memories and political and social changes and is sometimes unclear. At the same time, for those living as internally displaced people in their own countries, this question "where are you from" takes them to that wounded place in their memories.

The findings of a quantitative study on the concept of home among Ecuadorian immigrants in Madrid, Milan, and London, by Paolo Boccagni and Carlos Vargas-Silva (2021), suggested that concepts of home in these communities are deeply emotional, temporal, multiscale. The authors challenge the assumption that migrants' understandings of home lack ties to distinctive locations: Over time, Ecuadorian immigrants increasingly attribute a sense of home to their acquired local and national residential contexts; at the same time, their sense of home to their country-of-origin homeland decreases as the length of residence increases. This suggests that as immigrants progress through their life course, feeling at home and belonging becomes less about origin and ethnic or national belonging and more about perceived normality – a normality that tends to be experienced depending on gender (Boccagni & Vargas-Silva, 2021).

The possibility of having a home oscillates between memories of past loss, current conditions of violence, and the imagined hope of a better life for the future. Home is not only a shelter but also a place intertwined with history, belonging, identity, and social relations (Biner, 2019). This idea is also important for my approach, as I also explore the IDPs' concept of "home" not only as a

physical space, but also as a multi-layered meaning related to memory, identity, and social relations.

Research from across the globe on the concept of "home" has helped to draw a varied and shaded picture of home/homemaking in different socio-economic, climatic, and political contexts and different regimes of value. In the study of Feng and Breitung (Feng & Breitung, 2018) about the Chinese mega-cities of Hong Kong and Shenzhen, the authors find that social contacts are the key factor in the development of home construction. Functional factors such as housing, workplace, and home ownership also play a less important role than social connections. Homeownership, especially in Shenzhen, holds special significance and reflects the emphasis on establishing roots in a rapidly changing environment. Contrary to traditional concepts, nostalgic factors such as childhood memories and ancestry have relatively little influence on the concept of home; instead, practical considerations and social relations take priority. Place identity factors are also seen as less important; participants prioritize experience-based factors over imagination-based factors. These findings question common assumptions on certain values and emotional attachments in home-making processes. They challenge ethnographers, especially ethnographers "at home" to listen closely to their informants and to understand their concepts of homemaking beyond politically endorsed narratives.

The sense of coming home can be explained or used in different contexts. As an example, the theory of homecoming developed after World War II provides a valuable framework for understanding the challenges of the transition from military service. Soldiers, family members, and friends returning home have unique experiences during separation. Traveling home involves reestablishing relationships despite these changes. Homecoming theory highlights the theme of disconnection or alienation as part of the challenges facing returning veterans (Ahern et al., 2015). But this approach is not limited to veterans. It is also applied in anthropology and migration studies to understand the experiences of returnees, diaspora communities, and immigrants. Key figures in this field include researchers such as Catherine Nash, David Parkin, and Allison Blunt. Their work allows us to use the concept of homecoming in a broader context, linking it to space, memory, identity, and trauma. My research falls within this framework. The concept of homecoming is not only a physical return, but also a psychological and social reconnection process. The return to Karabakh is similar; the abandoned places have changed not only physically, but also socially and

culturally. Just as the soldiers face the disconnection they experience when they return home, the people, some of whom have also had to fight in the war, while others lost close ones in the war, returning to Karabakh also go through a process of reconnecting with the new spatial and a bloodstained reality. This study explores the experiences of memory and identity related to home, place, and space of people who were internally displaced from Karabakh and had the opportunity to return to their homeland after the Second Karabakh War in 2020. The process of returning to Karabakh and its relationship with human memory, identity, and space is the main topic of this study. In this context, homecoming theory is of particular importance.

The theme of homecoming is a recurring theme in both literature and scholarship, particularly in Thomas Wolfe's "You Can't Go Home Again" (Wolfe, 1934) and "The Return of the Prodigal" (Wolfe, 1987).. In these works, Wolfe explores the concepts of "home" and "homecoming" and describes the crises and feelings of alienation that his characters experience upon returning to their hometowns in a changing environment and a modernizing society. According to the writer, "home" is not just a physical place, but also a collection of memories, feelings, and social bonds that change over time. Both works show that it is impossible to truly return to a home in the past because people, places, and relationships are constantly changing, and these changes also shape an individual's identity and sense of belonging. Wolfe's ideas on this topic emphasize that homecoming is not just a physical experience, but also a complex emotional, cultural, and social experience.

Within the framework of the restoration and resettlement projects in Karabakh, a new "smart home" concept is being implemented, and these houses embody the modern concept of space. However, the spiritual value of such spaces for people and their connection to memory are different. The same theme is also touched upon in George Orwell's novel "Coming Up for Air". The novel tells the story of middle-aged George Bowling returning to his childhood town in search of his past and lost memories. However, the drastic changes he encounters, especially his childhood home, now turned into a tea shop, shattering his idealized image of the past, symbolizing the erosion of personal identity tied to familiar places. Orwell uses Bowling's disappointment to critique the social transformations in pre- and post-war England, contrasting the warmth of the old world with the alienation of modern life. The novel highlights how physical spaces carry social and cultural values, and how their loss affects personal and collective memory. From an

anthropological perspective, *Coming Up for Air* illustrates how space, memory, and identity interact, offering valuable insights into how people navigate returning to transformed places after war and societal change (Orwell, 1939).

By examining these different perspectives, from anthropological studies of displacement and resettlement to literature examining individuals' deep emotional and psychological ties to home, this thesis aims to illuminate how what it means to feel at home and to experience homesickness is more complex than meets the eye. The Karabakh case provides a unique and important example of how returning home is not just a geographical return, but also a deeply emotional, social, and political process. This is important because it shows that space is not just a physical space but is intertwined with identity, belonging, and collective memory.

In recent years, a rich literature has emerged from anthropological perspectives on the themes of "homecoming," "return," "nostalgia," and "displacement." For example, Lenhard and Samanani (2020) present experiences of "home," "dwelling," and "belonging" in diverse contexts in their collection *Home: Ethnographic Encounters*, Samanani's struggle with homelessness in London, Roth's informal settlement practices in Baku, Wagner's ethnography with Syrian refugees in Jordan. Sascha Roth (2020) explores the tensions between home and privacy in post-Soviet Baku, while Ann-Christin Wagner (2020) explores the notion of "temporary home" among internally displaced persons. Johannes Lenhard (2020) describes "homemaking" methods with street dwellers in Paris, and Max Ott (2020) describes creative home-building within a Berlin squat community. In my dissertation, I also illuminate the adaptation to historical, social, and cultural changes and the notions of "home" of IDPs returning from Karabakh by comparing them with existing work. My interviews show that they also have mixed feelings, as described by Roth, Wagner, and Lenhard, directed towards nostalgia, reestablishing social relations with space, and hopes for the future. Thus, this dissertation explores the topic not only in the context of Karabakh but also within a comparative framework drawn from global ethnographic practices.

1.1. Home in Azerbaijani Culture. Impacts of the Karabakh Conflict on “Azerbaijanism”

Azerbaijani identity has benefited from various cultural sources throughout its history: Turkic nomadic epics and language, Shiism from Iran, Sunnism from the Arab and Ottoman Empires, governance and industrialization from Russia, and Western values from Europe. In historical perspective, this identity was formed under various political regimes during the Russian Empire, the brief period of independence in 1918-1920, the Soviet period, and the post-Soviet period. In the 20th century, the process of national identification shifted from the framework of being Turkic alone to the concept of Azerbaijaniness – a broader and citizenship-based concept of national identity. Overall, if we consider its recent dynamics, especially during the twentieth century, the process of transformation prevails in the national identification of people, moving away from the narrow concept of Turkishness to Azerbaijanism (Azərbaycançılıq in Azerbaijani) - a broader concept of citizenship - to the concept of national identity without denying the Turkic element of Azerbaijani identity. At the local level, there is a high sense of unity among people in Azerbaijan. A strong sense of "we" exists among community members. This is based more on the idea of a unified state and society, without denying the Turkish element. Azerbaijani nationalism also comes with certain territorial imaginations/ desires, international allies and antagonists, as well as with a specific historical narrative, all of which have become sources of international and interethnic controversy, friction, and escalation since/ but also, as you say, a source for creating belonging and ideas of home. I think it would be important to show Azerbaijanism on the one hand as a source of international controversy, and on the other, as a source of national identity building/ of imagining a homeland, and the emerging ambivalence and tension. This collective consciousness is structurally double and consists of a shared past, a bond of destiny, and a common desired future. The present, which lives as their nexus, unites both and thus makes the whole reality of people's daily lives. The national idea acts as a source of both international and ethnic conflicts, as well as of perceptions of belonging and homeland. Azerbaijanism is, on the one hand, a subject of international debate, and on the other, the main ideological support for the construction of national identity and the perception of homeland. This collective consciousness consists of a shared understanding of the past and a desired future, and the present, which connects these two lines, shapes people's daily lives.

Among the events that accelerated this process, the independence movement from the Soviet Union and the war with Armenia are of particular importance. The independence movement that began around the Karabakh issue in 1988 and the January 20 incident of 1990 were examples of the unification of the people around the idea of freedom, regardless of ethnic differences. The tragedies of Black January and the Karabakh war, especially the Khojaly massacre of 1992, have become key events that shape the emotional memory of national unity. These tragedies have been included in both educational programs and social policies, strengthening ideas of a future land and a sense of belonging (Babayev & Abushov, 2022).

Black January was one of the bloodiest events in Azerbaijani history, marking a turning point in the struggle for national identity. Amid the escalating Karabakh conflict, the Azerbaijan Popular Front Party (APFP) emerged in 1989, gaining mass support through public rallies. Perceiving this as a threat to Soviet rule, Moscow responded with brutal repression. On the night of January 19-20, 1990, Soviet special forces, under Gorbachev's orders, entered Baku, killing 137 civilians and injuring many others. Soviet troops indiscriminately targeted civilians, including women and children, crushed ambulances with tanks, and used internationally banned bullets. The crackdown did not differentiate among Azerbaijani Turks, Jews, or Russians. Meanwhile, the Soviets arrested 43 APFP activists, sending some to Moscow's Lefortovo prison. As tensions escalated, paramilitary groups on both sides grew stronger, seeking military solutions. Reports indicated arms transfers from Armenia to Karabakh, with weapons arriving from Beirut via Yerevan. By June 1991, the conflict had claimed 816 lives, further fueling instability in the region (Karakoç, 2011).

Black January is an annual day of mourning and national remembrance in Azerbaijan. Every year, thousands of people visit the Alley of Martyrs in Baku, where the martyrs are buried, and pay their respects by laying wreaths and lighting candles. The event is marked by official ceremonies, speeches by state officials, and minutes of silence. Streets and public buildings are decorated with black ribbons, and national television channels broadcast documentaries and testimonies from survivors. Similarly, Azerbaijanis living outside the country come together to mark the day of remembrance in embassy and diaspora events. After the Black January incident, negative feelings arose in Azerbaijani society towards the Soviet Union, especially the Soviet army. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, relations between independent Azerbaijan and Russia went through various stages. The attitude towards Russia is more complex than during the Soviet period. The

memory of Black January still creates certain emotional tensions towards Russia in Azerbaijan, but this is because modern Azerbaijani-Russian relations often develop based on pragmatic and political interests.

1.2. On the Excursion: The Role of Black January and Its Role in the National Historiography of Azerbaijan

If we look through the historical path of the development of Azerbaijanism, I would like to mention the brief context of the creation of this term. The APFP came to power in 1992-93 amidst the disastrous conditions of the deepening First Karabakh War and internal strife. The Popular Front Party of Azerbaijan defended the concept of the Azerbaijani nation as an indivisible geographical and ethnic unit that transcended the unjustly divided Azerbaijani-Iranian border in the 19th century. This approach reinforced the fear of irredentism in the Iranian government, as the national identity of Azerbaijanis living in Iran hardened. After the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, Azerbaijanism became the state ideology under Heydar Aliyev. His speeches and policies presented Azerbaijanism as the basis of national unity, uniting both Azerbaijani Turks and ethnic minorities. After Heydar Aliyev returned to power in 1993, especially against the backdrop of the Karabakh war and the threat of separatism, Heydar Aliyev's national state-building project, especially against the backdrop of the Karabakh war and the threat of separatism, aimed not only to create a strong state identity, but also to ensure recognition and support for Azerbaijan's territorial integrity at the international level. In this context, Azerbaijanism took shape as a more inclusive and region-based state identity, moving away from the ethno-nationalism of the era of former president Abulfaz Elchibey. The Constitution of Azerbaijan defines citizens of the country as "citizens residing in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan", and only citizenship is recorded on passports and ID cards. The Constitution considers the preservation of territorial integrity and border changes possible only through a referendum. The fact that Nakhchivan's autonomy is administrative, not ethnic, also strengthens the citizenship-based structure of the state. However, demographic problems left over from the Soviet era and difficulties in the statistical representation of minorities persist (Broers & Mahmudlu, 2023).

1.3. Home in the Azerbaijani Concept and House as Home.

Home and place factors are deeply intertwined with nationalism in Azerbaijan. In Azerbaijan, a sense of belonging to the homeland is shaped not only by historical memories but also by everyday interactions with places and cultural symbols. From national monuments to street names, physical and symbolic spaces constantly reinforce collective identity. The memory of lost territories, especially Nagorno-Karabakh, further strengthened the emotional connection between people and place, making territorial integrity a central theme of Azerbaijani nationalism. After being part of the Soviet Union for many years and gaining independence in 1991, it tried to revive its nationalism. In the post-Soviet space and especially in the transition period of Azerbaijan, the central role of nationalism in national state-building processes, against two competing national ideologies such as “Turkism” and “Azerbaijanism”, and recently in the revival of national cultural traditions such as music and dance - all this emphasizes the importance of nationalism in its many manifestations in Azerbaijan. People feel like they belong to Azerbaijan in banal moments of affective encounters between specific places, different bodies, and objects (Militz & Schurr, 2015). One of the factors that played a decisive role in the formation of Azerbaijani identity was the loss of Nagorno-Karabakh and its surrounding territories in the 1991-1993 war. The war in the newly independent country mobilized Azerbaijanis who demanded the protection of their lands from their government. The protesters’ slogans were for the protection of the territorial unity of Azerbaijan. After the Khojaly massacre, Azerbaijani society became even more mobilized and began to resist as a united force. This began to manifest itself both in protests and in citizens voluntarily enlisting on the frontline. The Nagorno-Karabakh conflict ultimately strengthened not only Azerbaijani ethnic nationalism but also the nation's territorial concept. From the beginning of the 20th century, although Azerbaijanis had many identities (Muslim, Turkish, Soviet), the territorial-national (Azerbaijani) identity prevailed. The rhetoric of "Azerbaijanism", as well as the impact of the Nagorno-Karabakh war, strengthened the shared sense of national identity and homeland among the Azerbaijani people (Meneshian, 2021).

In Azerbaijani culture, the house is more understood in the sense of a place set aside for protection, separated from the environment, and built for personal privacy. Therefore, the fences of the houses built are high and in such a way that the inside cannot be seen from the outside. We can say that walls and fences are an important factor in the houses being built. The main reason for this is the

combination of the terms "home" and "family" in Azerbaijani culture under the belief of privacy/secrecy. It is no coincidence that there are many proverbs related to the house, such as "The house is ours, the secret is ours" (in Azerbaijani "Ev bizim, sirr bizim"). The large number of such proverbs and their coming from the past to the present day also show that the home culture rests on the past periods of Azerbaijani culture.

When the concept of privacy and its manifestation in Azerbaijani culture is examined through the lens of home architecture and social practices, it highlights the importance of privacy in Azerbaijani culture, where homes are often surrounded by walls to protect residents from public view. It extends to public spaces where he uses walls to hide less desirable areas from view. The predominance of walls and closed objects in Baku reflects the inviolability of private life. Traditionally, the architecture of Azerbaijani village houses has walled features, and post-socialist urban development has also seen a resurgence in the construction of walled houses. Although physical boundaries such as walls and curtains provide a sense of privacy, they reflect the collective nature of privacy in the home and the importance of protecting family members from public scrutiny (Roth, 2020).

People's vision of the future in Azerbaijan is not primarily individual, but rather social, and thus goes beyond their happiness. The most important part of people's vision of a good life is having children, seeing them as educated and married, and then having grandchildren. This approach is outlined in Babayev and Abushov's article "The Azerbaijani Resilient Society" (2022). The data collection method for the article was Focus Group Discussions (FGD). The research is based on 10 focus group discussions conducted in the four largest cities of Azerbaijan: Baku, Ganja, Sheki, and Lankaran. Each focus group included participants from different age groups and social statuses. The discussions lasted approximately 90-120 minutes and included students, civil servants, journalists, teachers, and retirees. I would also like to mention other findings based on the data from the focus groups. Azerbaijani society is primarily characterized by being organized around local communities of close relatives and neighbors. Azerbaijanis' trust in their family members, relatives, friends, and close neighbors is generally very high compared to people they don't know. When needed, family members and parents are the first to support. With this, we can say that the sustainability of Azerbaijani communities is primarily based on local support infrastructure, such as relatives or friends. Individuals thrive mostly through family and kinship

networks, such as finding a job or gaining access to resources. The family also plays an important role in the formation of social identity. Therefore, there are strong family bonds, and even when individuals start their own families, they have a strong bond with their parents. From this point of view, the central role of the family in Azerbaijani society is not only related to the relatively slow economic and social modernization or the relative weakness of the state, but more importantly, it is related to the traditions and norms that have come so far. Family is a must in Azerbaijani society, and it is taken for granted that the ultimate goal of every individual is to have a family. Unlike feelings of family and kinship, the neighborhood's relationship to the wider community or social solidarity is more straightforward. In good times or bad, neighbors help each other financially and provide moral support as good protection. However, the concept of the neighborhood already existed and was applied in the old buildings and settlements of Baku from the Soviet era, and did not transfer to new skyscrapers and residential complexes (Babayev & Abushov, 2022).

Babayev and Abushov's (2022) study shows that family and neighborhood relations are strong social supports in Azerbaijani society. However, it is important to understand how these relations manifest themselves among internally displaced persons. How have neighborhood relations, social trust, and support systems changed in villages and new settlements where different ethnic groups lived together in historical periods? For this reason, I believe that interviews with displaced families will allow for a deeper exploration of the topic and an understanding of social continuity.

Of course, today the integration between cities or from the countryside to the city continues at a faster pace. Nevertheless, the places and houses left behind are waiting to be visited by their old inhabitants. Especially, these happen during the holidays in Azerbaijani culture. So, people return to their native places from the cities for a short time, visit their relatives, acquaintances, and villages, and even visit the graves of their relatives. Regarding the rites performed on the eve of the holiday, as Turkhan Sadigov mentioned, we can say that especially on the eve of Novruz, everyone, including those living in other cities and regions, returns to their native villages/towns and visits the graves of their relatives and loved ones. There, they recite prayers for them and place torches on their graves¹ (Sadigov, 2018).

¹ Of course, when we talk about visiting the homes and graves of our ancestors, Azerbaijanis who were held captive for 6.5 years come to mind. Without judging their rightness or wrongness, Azerbaijanis who secretly traveled to their homeland and the graves of their relatives in 2014 to see their childhood homes and parental graves —

In order to preserve the cultural heritage, promoting the customs and traditions of the Azerbaijani people, taking measures for the preservation of national holidays and ceremonies, national music and dances, folklore, restoration and development of national games are among the nuances that the people of Azerbaijan pay attention to, and the article written about it and studies confirm this. The family plays a special role in state policy in the field of protecting the cultural heritage of the people, and it continues to do so as a thought. Along with the state, the family is the main protector of the national traditions of Azerbaijani folk pedagogy. To achieve this goal, I think the role of education that transmits cultural values from generation to generation should also be emphasized (Nuruzade, 2017). At the same time, the family is not only the custodian of cultural heritage, but also a social space where the concept of home and marriage is restored. Through the stories and memories told among family members, individuals reconstruct a sense of home and belonging. This process brings to the fore the issue of storytelling and the transmission of memory, which will also play an important role in future interviews.

1.4. Population Composition in Azerbaijan and Armenia

Analyzing the larger process of ethnic homogeneity in both Armenia and Azerbaijan after the fall of the Soviet Union requires an understanding of their respective ethnic compositions. Demographic structures have been profoundly impacted by the region's conflicts and violent upheavals, which have affected the likelihood of interethnic cohabitation. A better understanding of these changes and their effects on the development of national identity may be obtained by looking at demographic data.

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the ethnic composition and national relations in the South Caucasus underwent serious changes. The armed conflicts between Azerbaijan and Armenia and the Karabakh conflict dealt a heavy blow to the multinational living structure of the region. If

Dilgam Asgarov and Shahbaz Guliyev — were captured by Armenian soldiers, and Hasan Hasanov was killed. Dilgam was sentenced to life imprisonment, and Shahbaz to 22 years in prison. They were released and returned to Azerbaijan on December 14, 2020, as part of the ceasefire agreement in the 2020 Karabakh war and the exchange of prisoners and hostages between Azerbaijan and Armenia, mediated by international organizations (Shahbaz Guliyev was born in 1968 in the village of Gapanli in the Tartar District of the Azerbaijani SSR. Before the July 2014 incident, Asgarov lived and worked in Russia, cutting trees and selling wood, coming home only infrequently to see his family).

Source: BBC News Azerbaijan, 2020.

during the Soviet period the population of Azerbaijan included more than 100 thousand Armenians, more than 300 thousand Russians and other peoples, because of conflicts and successive migration processes, these numbers decreased sharply. Although a small Armenian community does not formally exist in Azerbaijan today, there is unofficial information that there are people of Armenian origin in Baku and some cities who continue to live by changing their surnames and identities. However, the state has taken a more conservative position in its attitude towards examples of religious and cultural heritage - the 19th-century St. Gregory the Armenian Church, located in the center of Baku, is still preserved today and is sometimes open to visits by foreign religious delegations (Azerbaijan Statistical Information Service, 2024), (Religions.az, 2024).

Photo 1: Saint Gregory the Illuminator's Armenian Church in Baku. Source: www.religions.az

At the same time, to assess the situation from another perspective, I should note that the website of Armenia's official statistical agency, ARMSTAT, does not share statistics on the ethnic composition of the population and national minorities. Instead, according to data from the international NGO Minority Rights Group, the conflict that began in the early 1990s has radically changed the demographic landscape of Armenia. As a result of the conflict, more than 180,000 Azerbaijanis and thousands of Kurds, the largest minority in the country, were forcibly displaced. Nationalism and xenophobia have intensified in both countries, which has also been encouraged by the governments. In 2021, the International Court of Justice imposed interim measures to

prevent racial discrimination against both states and required Armenia to stop incitement to hatred against Azerbaijanis. Currently, national minorities in Armenia make up less than 2% of the population and, as they live scattered throughout the country, have limited opportunities for socio-political representation. They were allocated four seats in the 2021 parliamentary elections. The official state language is Armenian only, and there is no policy to promote the development of minority languages and cultures. Education and university exams are also conducted only in Armenian. Although Russian, Assyrian, Yazidi, and Kurdish are taught in some regions, these classes are not taught in most schools due to a lack of textbooks and teachers. State television and radio, however, devote only 30 minutes (TV) and 2 hours (radio) per week to minority languages and cultures. This creates serious educational and social barriers for the Yazidi community in particular (Minority Rights Group, 2024a).

1.5. Migration Patterns in Azerbaijan: A Country of Diverse Movements and the Importance of Forced Migration

Azerbaijan has long been a country shaped by diverse migration movements, reflecting both historical and contemporary socio-economic dynamics.

Migration in Azerbaijan is not limited to forced displacement; it also includes labor migration, student mobility, and rural-urban migration. Many Azerbaijani workers seek work abroad, while Azerbaijani students form large communities in various countries. In addition, Azerbaijan has historically faced immigration from neighboring countries (for example, Russia, Türkiye), as well as internal migration driven by economic opportunities in urban centers.

However, despite this diversity, forced migration stands out as one of the most striking and traumatic experiences in Azerbaijani society. In particular, the conflicts in the Karabakh region, in the post-Soviet period, have played a decisive role in shaping migration patterns. Wars and violent escalation have not only displaced large populations but have also significantly changed the ethnic and demographic landscape of Azerbaijan and Armenia. The next section will discuss the forced displacements caused by the Karabakh conflict and their lasting impact on Azerbaijani society.

2. FORCED MIGRATION. MIGRATION IN AZERBAIJAN AND THE ROLE OF INTERNAL DISPLACEMENTS FROM KARABAKH

The concept of forced or involuntary migration encompasses both refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) as recognized under international law, as well as people displaced by war, ethnic conflict, and government policies. Although these people are often referred to colloquially as “refugees,” this is a narrow approach and does not include everyone under this status at the international level. Many internally displaced persons are displaced within their own country and do not receive refugee status. According to the 1951 UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees, a refugee is a person who, owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion, is unable to return to his or her country of origin. Currently, approximately 140 of the world’s 190 countries have ratified this convention and have committed to complying with its rules, in particular the principle of non-refoulement (Castles, 2003). The definition made by UNHCR (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees) is essentially refugees, people who cross the border to another country to escape conflict, persecution, and human rights violations. When refugees arrive in a safe place, they are usually hungry, traumatized, and exhausted after a long and dangerous journey, many carrying nothing but clothes on their backs, looking for shelter and protection. UNHCR, which has been operating in 136 countries for over 70 years today to help refugees, was established in 1950 by the United Nations General Assembly after World War II (WW II) to help millions of people who had lost their homes. Guided by the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, and acting as the guardian of these conventions, UNHCR also defines asylum seekers, and we can state that it is "persons who have fled their country of origin and have applied for asylum in another country but whose request for refugee status has not yet been processed". According to UNHCR, an asylum seeker will not automatically be recognized as a refugee, but every refugee initially enters a new country as an asylum seeker. Millions of people worldwide are denied citizenship, leaving them stateless and without critical documents such as birth certificates. As a result, they often live without being allowed to go to school, see a doctor, find a job, open a bank account, vote, travel, or even buy a home (UNHCR, 2024).

It would be useful to briefly mention the research of authors who examine both the anthropological and emotional effects of migration, as well as its economic impact. Migration is not only shaped by emotions and identity but also by economic factors. For instance, the journal article by Isabel Ruiz and Carlos Vargas-Silva (2013) highlights that migration influences the economy while also being driven by economic conditions. This perspective helps bridge the emotional and economic dimensions of migration, showing how financial concerns and emotional ties to home interact in the migration experience. For example, when discussing forced migration, the first place that comes to mind for many people is the result of civil wars in the African continent or violence in the Middle East. However, a significant part of the economic literature on the effects of forced migration also looks at the impact of European forced migration movements resulting from events related to WW II. These studies provide a fascinating perspective, as it is possible to observe the long-term consequences of forced migration for those forced to migrate. At the same time, the article examines the short- and medium-term effects of hosting forced migrants, noting the lack of long-term economic studies on this issue. A key argument is that the degree of interaction between refugees and locals in the labor market significantly shapes the economic consequences of displacement. In some cases, forced migrants complement the local workforce and contribute positively, while in others, they may act as substitutes, potentially leading to competition. This discussion is relevant to my research as it highlights the economic dimensions of forced migration, which intersect with the broader social and political implications of displacement. Understanding these dynamics can help analyze how migration policies and economic structures influence the integration and long-term prospects of displaced populations (Ruiz & Vargas-Silva, 2013). The instance of Karabakh, where widespread forced migration brought on by violence has had significant economic and social repercussions, makes this topic more pertinent. The complicated interactions between migration, labor markets, and economic restructuring are shown by the Azerbaijanis' exodus from Karabakh in the early 1990s and subsequent return during the Second Karabakh War. Analyzing how economic structures and migration policies affect the integration and long-term prospects of displaced people can be made easier with an understanding of these processes.

Çağlar and Schiller's method profoundly inspired me as I worked on the idea of forced migration, and it has shaped my anthropological viewpoint. Their emphasis on the processes of forced

migrants' identity construction and settling offers a useful foundation for my studies on acculturation to new environments and ultimate return to former residences. I want to learn how forced migrants create survival plans and contribute to the communities they settle in by looking at these processes. Çağlar and Schiller's "multiscalar" analyses, which highlight the local and global dynamics of city development through multi-layered studies of migration and urban change, have helped me better comprehend the roles that migrants play in urban settlement processes. Ayşe Çağlar and Nina Glick Schiller's book "Migrants and City-Making: Dispossession, Displacement, and Urban Regeneration" (2018) examines forced migration in the context of urban settlement processes and urban restructuring. The book examines the settlement processes of migrants by focusing on three different cities: Mardin in Türkiye, Manchester in New Hampshire, USA, and Halle/Saale in Germany. It discusses how migrants and local people play roles in city-making and how migrant settlements transform economic and social relations in the city. The main part of the book discusses how the processes of forced displacement are combined with how migrants settle and resettle in cities. Migrants are not seen as merely "foreigners"; on the contrary, they are considered to have influential social roles in city-making (Çağlar & Glick Schiller, 2018). My theoretical viewpoint on forced migration in Azerbaijan, particularly about IDPs, is pertinent to this study. It challenges the notion that ethnic identification alone shapes integration and belonging, arguing that a variety of factors, including social, religious, and economic networks, can affect how forced migrants in Azerbaijan adapt to and integrate into new contexts. Like the instances studied in the paper, it also promotes a more comprehensive knowledge of how local factors in Azerbaijan, particularly in smaller cities or regions, might impact IDPs' integration trajectories.

2.1. Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs)

There is a subtle distinction to be made between refugees and internally displaced persons. Although people with both statuses are forcibly displaced from their homes and lives, they have commonalities as well as points that distinguish them. A distinction is often made between IDPs

and refugees, who face similar conditions but have important legal and conceptual differences. I have already mentioned that the 1951 Refugee Convention defines them as those who cross international borders due to fear of persecution, threats, and risk to their lives, such as race, religion, or political opinion. However, internally displaced persons continue their new lives by remaining in their own countries and without the benefit of international protection frameworks like refugees. They start anew from where they left off as foreigners in their own countries. According to the Internal Displacement Guiding Principles, if we need to specify the definition of IDPs, we can say this definition: "Persons or groups of persons who are forced to leave their homes or places of permanent residence without crossing internationally recognized borders, especially because of armed conflict, widespread violence, human rights violations or natural and man-made disasters". Unlike refugees, IDPs remain under the jurisdiction of their own country, which means that the state has the primary responsibility to protect them. In other words, they are under the responsibility of their own country to protect them. We see this more in geographies where parts of the country are occupied (Phuong, 2005). People are not only displaced due to invasions, and forced to live in other houses. Forcibly internally displaced persons are grouped under different categories. These include displacement due to conflict, violence, and human rights violations, displacement due to natural disasters such as earthquakes and floods, displacement due to man-made disasters such as nuclear or chemical accidents, and displacement due to major development projects such as the construction of dams, roads, and military positions (Mooney, 2005).

I would like to mention another article written on IDPs that contains a detailed review (Leus et al., 2001). This article focuses on the health and security problems faced by displaced people and mentions that one of the biggest challenges for displaced people living in conflict and war zones is the lack of access to basic health services. It is argued that in addition to their lack of security, they also have difficulty accessing basic needs such as water, shelter, and food. This situation poses a risk of epidemics and high mortality rates. It is argued that providing health services alone is not enough to save the lives of displaced people, and humanitarian assistance must be comprehensive, meaning that basic needs must be met. Although the responsibility for assisting displaced people primarily lies with national governments, in many cases, governments fail to fulfill this responsibility. In this case, the international community steps in. The World Health Organization (WHO) plays an important role in coordinating humanitarian assistance in the field of health.

Community participation is of great importance in this regard. It is argued that communities should actively assist in using their assets. WHO also encourages providing health services to displaced persons and humanitarian assistance to protect their rights and respond to their needs

It is known that internally displaced persons (IDPs) face not only the problem of finding shelter, but also psychological difficulties. Although more than 65.6 million people worldwide have been displaced as a result of armed conflicts, information on their mental health is limited. One of the articles that touches on this topic is the study “Psychiatric Disorders in Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons After Forced Displacement: A Systematic Review” published in 2018 by Naser Morina, Aemal Akhtar, Jürgen Barth and Ulrich Schnyder. The article analyzed the data obtained as a result of a search conducted in the Medline, PsycINFO, PILOTS and Cochrane Library databases with the keywords “mental health”, “refugees”, “internal migrants”, “survey” and “war”. As a result, 38 studies on 39,518 internally displaced persons and refugees from 21 countries were studied. The most common mental disorders were Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (3-88%), depression (5-80%), and anxiety disorders (1-81%). The study showed that there is a lack of information about mental health problems of people living in protracted displacement situations and a need for large-scale interventions (Morina et al., 2018). All these indicators indicate that special caution and methodological sensitivity are required when conducting research on internally displaced persons, taking into account their traumatic experiences and psychological states.

Another research article, focusing on the health problems of internally displaced persons and making recommendations for improving health services for these people, examines the role and effectiveness of mobile clinics in humanitarian crises and presents findings on how these clinics increase access to health services. The use of mobile clinics in emergencies is recommended as an effective method to increase access to health services. At the same time, the psychiatric disorders seen in forcibly displaced people and the importance of mental health services for these people are emphasized, and the importance of group therapy and counseling services for the treatment of psychiatric disorders is stated as a solution to this as a finding of the research. At the same time, one of the most important issues that should not be ignored is infectious diseases, their spread in war and conflict zones, and the methods of combating this are addressed, and the integration of vaccination services, especially increasing the vaccination rates of children, is suggested as a solution to this (Cantor et al., 2021).

It is obvious that counting and giving exact statistics about the refugees and IDPs all over the world is too complicated and it is hard to measure the exact numbers for all the reasons. But if we consider the number of IDPs getting assistance from the organizations, it can be considered.

Country	Population start-2015 Total	Population end-2015 Total
Afghanistan	805,409	1,174,306
Azerbaijan	622,892	618,220
Bosnia and Herzegovina	84,500	98,324
Burundi	78,948	25,000
Cameroon	-	92,657
Central African Rep.	438,538	216,392
Chad	-	51,999
Colombia	6,044,151	6,939,067
Côte d'Ivoire	24,000	308,272
Dem. Rep. of the Congo	2,756,585	1,555,112
Georgia	262,704	268,416
Honduras	-	174,000
Iraq	3,596,356	4,403,287
Libya	363,067	434,869
Mali	99,816	61,920
Myanmar ¹	441,500	416,089
Myanmar (people in IDP-like situation) ¹	35,000	35,000
Niger	-	137,337
Nigeria	1,188,018	2,151,979
Nigeria (people in IDP-like situation) ²	-	20,553
Pakistan	1,375,904	1,146,108
Philippines	142,430	63,174
Serbia and Kosovo: S/RES/1244 (1999)	223,139	220,002
Somalia	1,133,000	1,133,000
South Sudan	1,490,195	1,685,427
South Sudan (people in IDP-like situation)	155,197	105,000
Sri Lanka ³	30,847	44,934
Sudan	2,115,530	3,218,234
Sudan (people in IDP-like situation)	77,300	-
Syrian Arab Rep.	7,632,500	6,563,462
Ukraine	823,000	800,000
Ukraine (people in IDP-like situation)	-	800,000
Yemen	334,093	2,532,032
Total	32,374,619	37,494,172

Table 1: Internally displaced persons (IDPs) protected/assisted by UNHCR | 2015. Source: UNHCR > Statistical Yearbook 2015

Based on the yearbook published by UNHCR in 2017, which included the statistical figures for 2015, the table above includes information only for IDPs protected or assisted by UNHCR. It should also be noted that these are not exact figures, as it is difficult to accurately reflect all IDPs living in each country. Furthermore, since UNHCR does not cover many IDP situations worldwide, they have not been reflected. The majority of IDP numbers are approximations, rounded to the closest hundredth (UNHCR, 2017).

Country / Territory	Year	Conflict Internal Displacement	Conflict IDPs	Disaster Internal Displacement
Azerbaijan	2023	5,100	658,000	1,700
Azerbaijan	2022		659,000	190
Azerbaijan	2021		655,000	
Azerbaijan	2020	84,000	735,000	
Azerbaijan	2019		651,000	140
Armenia	2023		7,600	
Armenia	2022	7,600	7,600	
Armenia	2021		800	
Armenia	2020	800	800	

Table 2: Internally displaced people (IDPs), Azerbaijan and Armenia. Source: www.internal-displacement.org (2025).

I think it is important to look at the statistics shared by the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC), another institution on which the statistical information provided by UNHCR is based, to understand the seriousness of the incident. First, I would like to share some brief information about the institution, which was established in 1998 as part of the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) and provides an independent service to the international community. It is the leading source of data and analysis on internal displacement. They play a role in informing policy and operational decisions to improve the lives of millions of people living in internal displacement or at risk of displacement in the future. The web pages specify the statistical figures and reasons for people subjected to forced internal displacement by categorizing them as country profiles. According to the statistics shared, a total of 46.9 million internal displacements were recorded in 151 countries and regions in 2023. As of the end of 2023, 75.9 million people were recorded to have been displaced due to conflict, violence, and disasters in 116 countries and regions. The data shared by IDMC was shared because of monitoring internal displacement for all countries and regions throughout the year (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre, 2024). IDPs often face serious challenges when it comes to returning. In some cases, return is not possible due to ongoing conflict, collapsed infrastructure, or hostile socio-political conditions. Even when return is physically possible, psychological trauma and loss of social ties make reintegration very difficult. In the Karabakh issue, Azerbaijanis who have been displaced for decades have not been able to

return to their homes, and it is only after recent political changes that the possibility of return has resurfaced, although it remains a complex and sensitive process.

3. THE HISTORY OF THE OCCUPATION OF KARABAKH AND ITS IMPACT ON BOTH NATIONS

While the history of the Karabakh region is not the main focus of this dissertation, it is essential to briefly outline key historical events to understand the roots of the conflict and contemporary politics around homecoming. Drawing on the works of Hikmet Demirci and other scholars, this section situates Karabakh in a broader geopolitical context. Between 1722-1747, under Nadir Shah, territories including Karabakh were temporarily ceded to Tsarist Russia. After his death, regional unity collapsed, and in the 19th century, Russia formally occupied Azerbaijani khanates like Ganja, Karabakh, and Baku through the Gulistan (1813) and Turkmenchay (1828) treaties, enabling Armenian settlement in the region. In 1828, Tsar Nicholas I established the "Armenian Province," laying the groundwork for modern Armenia. Ethnic tensions escalated in the early 20th century, notably with the March 1918 massacres of Azerbaijanis in Baku and surrounding areas. Though the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic declared independence in May 1918, Bolshevik forces occupied the country in 1920. In 1921, with Soviet support, Armenian armed groups carried out attacks against Azerbaijani populations in Yerevan, Nakhchivan, Karabakh, and Shusha. These historical shifts created long-lasting demographic and political changes, fueling the disputes that continue to shape the Karabakh issue today (Demirci, 2022).

As Karakoç argues, in the late 19th century, Russian authorities suppressed nationalist sentiments in the South Caucasus. Prince Golitsyn, appointed governor of Transcaucasia in 1876, closed Armenian schools and confiscated church property, triggering Armenian unrest. After his assassination in 1903, Count Vorontsov-Dashkov's appointment in 1905 marked a pro-Armenian shift, while Muslim clergy and property came under strict state control. Amid economic and ethnic tensions, the 1905 Russian Revolution sparked national movements and ethnic clashes. The first Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict broke out in Baku in 1905, following the murder of an Azerbaijani by a Dashnaktsutyun member. Violence quickly spread to Yerevan, Nakhchivan, Shusha, Ganja, and Tbilisi. By 1906, over 280 villages were looted or destroyed, with an estimated 3,100 to 10,000 casualties. The events received pro-Armenian coverage in global media, a narrative embraced by Armenian communities (Karakoç, 2011).

In March–April 1918, the Dashnak-Bolshevik regime led by Stepan Shaumyan carried out mass massacres against Azerbaijanis in Baku, Shamakhi, Guba, Karabakh, Lankaran, and other regions. Over 7,000 people were killed in Shamakhi alone, and more than 50,000 Azerbaijanis were murdered in total. These events are considered genocide based on national and religious identity. Mosques and cultural monuments were also destroyed. In 2007, a mass grave from the 1918 Guba massacre was uncovered, confirming the atrocities committed by Armenian Dashnak forces. Leaders such as Stepan Shaumyan, Shamazas, Lalayan, and Mikoyan were identified as key perpetrators. The 1918 Extraordinary Commission of Inquiry of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic documented these crimes, collecting extensive evidence from domestic and international archives. Shaumyan himself admitted in letters that the massacres in Baku and Shamakhi were deliberate. Despite abundant historical documentation, international recognition of the 1918 genocide remains limited, with primary support coming from the Islamic world and Azerbaijan's allies. Azerbaijan continues diplomatic, scientific, and cultural efforts for global recognition and annually commemorates March 31 as the Day of the Genocide of Azerbaijanis (Mahmudov & Valiyev, 2016).

The first volume of the 4-volume book, which is prepared by compiling the archive documents of Ali Merdan Bey Topchubashov and which deals with the documents and diplomatic efforts of the "Democratic Republic of Azerbaijan in the context of the Paris Peace Conference (1919-1921)," and compiled by G. Mamulia and R. Abutalıbov, was published in 2016. The book titled Paris Archive touches upon important points such as Azerbaijan's struggle for independence, international recognition initiatives, and relations with the great powers of the period. This work presents original documents, especially on the political history of Azerbaijan and international diplomacy. At the Paris Peace Conference, Azerbaijan was not recognized as a fully independent state, but it was accepted as a de facto administration. This situation was considered an important step in Azerbaijan's struggle for international recognition. During the Paris Peace Conference, the Democratic Republic of Azerbaijan gained de facto status, although it was not fully recognized as an independent state. This recognition was an important gain in terms of Azerbaijan's existence being accepted in the international arena. However, the interests of the great powers (especially France and England) limited Azerbaijan's ability to achieve its goal of full independence. As a result, the efforts at the Paris Peace Conference were a critical turning point for Azerbaijan's

international recognition, but this process remained largely dependent on the geopolitical balances of the period (Topchubashov, 2016) (pages: 17-45).

The historical claims over Nagorno-Karabakh by both Azerbaijanis and Armenians are explored. Both groups trace their roots to the region, with Armenians citing ancient settlements, while Azerbaijanis emphasize their long-standing governance and presence in the area. The area has shifted between various powers throughout history, further complicating the competing narratives. The Soviet era saw its designation as an autonomous oblast within Azerbaijan, creating underlying tensions. The conflict, rooted in territorial disputes and ethnic tensions, has resulted in significant casualties and displaced populations. It transitioned from an internal struggle for autonomy to an inter-state conflict involving Armenia and Azerbaijan. Despite numerous mediation attempts, the region's geopolitical importance has complicated resolution efforts, with minimal progress. Armenian and Azerbaijani populations were systematically displaced, escalating the conflict into ethnic violence (Cornell, 1999).

Armenian nationalism, encouraged by Tsarist Russia and later the Soviet Union, was shaped by demographic changes resulting from the resettlement of Armenians from the Ottoman Empire and Iran to Azerbaijani territories. In the 20th century, Armenian nationalism intensified around the idea of establishing a nation-state, with Karabakh at its center. Soviet authorities left Karabakh as an autonomous region within Azerbaijan, a status Armenia never fully accepted. This unresolved situation and Moscow's manipulative policies fueled ethnic tensions. From the late 1980s, Armenian nationalist groups used cultural, historical, and political claims, along with violence, to assert control over Karabakh, leading to war. During the conflict, hundreds of thousands of Azerbaijani Turks were forcibly displaced, and a de facto Armenian authority was established in violation of international law. The conflict's roots lie in Armenian nationalism and the strategic interference of Russia, which historically marginalized the rights of Azerbaijani Turks in the region (Otabatmaz, 2023).

The conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan in Nagorno-Karabakh has its roots in demographic changes that began in the 19th century and border manipulations by the Soviet leadership. The inclusion of Nagorno-Karabakh as a special autonomous region within Azerbaijan by Stalin in 1921 laid the foundation for the disputes. In 1988, the Armenian population of Nagorno-Karabakh petitioned for unification with Armenia, which increased conflicts with Azerbaijanis. In May 1992,

Armenian forces took control of the Lachin corridor, establishing direct contact between Armenia and Nagorno-Karabakh. This increased the military intensity of the conflict. As a result of the conflict, the cities of Aghdam, Fuzuli, and other Azerbaijani cities were occupied by Armenian forces and suffered widespread destruction. Although the conflict remained largely unnoticed internationally, it has reignited historical hostilities in the region. Countries such as Russia, the United States, Türkiye, and Iran have intervened in the conflict in various ways. In particular, Russia has sought to increase its influence in the region by forcing Azerbaijan to join the CIS. Diplomats' efforts to protect the borders have not achieved concrete progress in resolving the conflict, which provides the basis for the aggressive policy of Armenian forces (Uhlig, 1993).

Armenia has not officially recognized the independence of Nagorno-Karabakh. In 1991, the Nagorno-Karabakh Assembly declared independence, but this declaration was not recognized by the international community. Armenia attempted to annex Nagorno-Karabakh to its territory, but this step was not accepted internationally. The region declared itself as the "Republic of Artsakh" in 1991, but this declaration of independence was not recognized by any member of the international community (Paşa, 2021).

Name of settlement	Date of occupation
Karki village (Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic of the Republic of Azerbaijan)	15.01.1990
Baganis Ayrym (Gazakh district)	24.03.1990
Khankendi	28.12.1991
Khojaly	26.02.1992
Kheyrymly village (Gazakh district)	08.03.1992
Ashaghy Askipara (Gazakh district)	12.03.1992
Barkhudarly (Gazakh district)	27.04.1992
Sofulu (Gazakh district)	27.04.1992
Shusha	08.05.1992
Gyzylhajly (Gazakh district)	11.05.1992
Lachin	18.05.1992
Yukhary Askipara (Gazakh district)	08.06.1992

Khojavand	02.10.1992
Kalbajar	02.04.1993
Aghdara²	07.07.1993
Aghdam	23.07.1993
Fuzuli	23.08.1993
Jabrayil	23.08.1993
Gubadly	31.08.1993
Zangilan	29.10.1993

Table 3: The table of territories of Azerbaijan subjected to military occupation by Armenia. Source: Republic of Azerbaijan Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

If we approach the conflict from the perspective that the UN played a role in the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict primarily through the resolutions adopted by the Security Council. These resolutions were aimed at addressing the conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan, focusing on ending hostilities, preserving territorial integrity, and facilitating peaceful negotiations. It supported peace efforts led by regional organizations such as the OSCE Minsk Group. The Co-Chair countries of the OSCE Minsk Group reaffirm their commitment to working with the sides to find comprehensive solutions to all remaining issues related to or resulting from the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict following their mandate in order to promote a secure, stable, prosperous, and peaceful future for the South Caucasus region. The Minsk Group, whose activities became known as the Minsk Process, aimed to spearhead OSCE efforts to find a peaceful solution to the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. At its meeting in Helsinki in 1992, the then OSCE Council requested the Chairman-in-Office to convene a conference on the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict involving Armenia and Azerbaijan at the earliest possible opportunity, which was to be held in Minsk and provide a forum for negotiations towards a peaceful solution. In 1994, the OSCE Budapest Summit established the Minsk Group, which continued working to create conditions for such a conference to occur, co-chaired by France, the Russian Federation, and the United States (OSCE, 2024). In 1993, the UN Security Council adopted four key resolutions (822, 853, 874, and 884) to uphold

² Agdara district was abolished on October 13, 1992, and its territory was included in the administrative borders of Agdam, Kalbajar and Tartar districts. This decision was made to ensure more centralized administration due to the attack of Armenian armed forces on a large part of Agdara territory and the displacement of part of the population during the Karabakh war. Thus, Agdara was removed from the map of Azerbaijan as an administrative unit and its territory was distributed among neighboring districts.

Azerbaijan's territorial integrity, which had been violated by Armenian forces occupying areas around Nagorno-Karabakh. The conflict displaced over one million people, mostly Azerbaijanis. Resolution 884 condemned ceasefire violations and urged Armenia to ensure that Armenians in Nagorno-Karabakh comply with previous resolutions. It called for the immediate withdrawal of occupying forces from Zangilan, Goradiz, and other recently occupied Azerbaijani territories. The UN also emphasized restoring and maintaining the ceasefire, supported by Russia and the OSCE Minsk Group. Reiterates its call on all States in the region to refrain from any hostile action or any intervention that could lead to an expansion of the conflict and jeopardize peace and security in the region; requests the Secretary-General and relevant international organizations to provide urgent humanitarian assistance to the affected civilian population (UN. Security Council (48th year), 1993). But unfortunately, the last decision taken by the United Nations failed to have any effect on the conflict, just like the previous ones.

The United Nations General Assembly, at its 86th session on March 14, 2008, adopted a resolution supporting Azerbaijan's internationally recognized borders and demanding the immediate withdrawal of Armenian forces from Azerbaijani territory. The resolution was adopted with 39 countries voting in favor, 7 against, and 100 abstaining. This development underlined the fundamental principles of international law regarding the resolution of the conflict in and around Nagorno-Karabakh. The resolution reaffirmed the Azerbaijani population's right to return to their homes while stressing that no state should legally recognize the situation resulting from the occupation. At the same time, it emphasized the importance of ensuring safe and equal living conditions for the Armenian and Azerbaijani communities in Nagorno-Karabakh. The resolution adopted by the General Assembly reaffirmed the international community's support for Azerbaijan's territorial integrity. However, it emphasized that the parties must return to the negotiating table within the framework of international law in order to resolve the conflict peacefully (United Nations, 2008).

According to the scholar Baghdasaryan, between 1988 and 1992, approximately 360,000 Armenians migrated from Azerbaijan to Armenia during the early years of the Karabakh conflict. Initially, the Armenian state and people accepted these refugees as "national citizens" and provided them with temporary housing. However, with the collapse of the Soviet Union and the war, Armenia experienced a serious economic crisis. The biggest problem of the migrants was that they

could not get back the properties they left behind and could not obtain permanent housing in Armenia. Although the state provided them with temporary settlements, the demand for permanent housing for the refugees became a priority. Although the Armenian government simplified the citizenship procedures and offered citizenship to the refugees, 30% of the refugees rejected this offer without receiving assurance that the state would provide permanent housing. In her article published in 2011, Armenian researcher Milena Baghdasaryan examined the perception of social citizenship by refugees in Armenia regarding housing problems and the state's approach to solving this problem. She also revealed in her research that social citizenship practices in Armenia were shaped by the understandings inherited from the Soviet period, but there were serious restrictions on the implementation of these rights due to economic difficulties and the state's limited resources (Baghdasaryan, 2011).

I would like to dedicate a special place to several articles and facts to take a separate look at the Khojaly genocide, which may be recorded as the most painful memory of the war in the 1990s. The Khojaly tragedy is one of the most horrific massacres of the Nagorno-Karabakh war. In February 1992, Armenian forces attacked Khojaly, killing a large number of Azerbaijani civilians³. The tragedy left a deep and painful mark on Azerbaijan's collective memory. In February 1992, Armenian forces attacked Khojaly⁴, targeting Azerbaijanis under siege in the region, to seize the strategic airport. Since then, efforts have been made to raise global awareness of the tragedy. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation, established in 2004, has played a key role in these efforts, organizing commemorations in various countries and advocating for international recognition. Resolutions recognizing and condemning the Khojaly tragedy have been adopted in countries such as Pakistan, Colombia, Mexico, Türkiye, Bosnia, Serbia, Romania, and the Czech Republic. In the United States, many state legislatures (Texas, New Jersey, Massachusetts, etc.) have adopted resolutions and issued statements regarding the Khojaly tragedy. The memorials and monuments that

³ 613 people were killed, including 63 children; 106 women; 70 elderly. 8 families were completely annihilated; 25 children lost both parents; 130 children lost one parent.

- 487 wounded.
- 1275 taken hostage.
- 150 still missing.

Source: Xocali.org; mod.gov.az; bbc.com

⁴ It is possible to access the facts about the genocide in Khojaly, facts about the event, and photos taken by photographers from different countries (Russian, Armenian, French) via the following link: http://xocali.org/en/index.php?p=photo_archive (date of access 27.03.2025).

Azerbaijan has built in countries such as Bosnia, Mexico, and Türkiye also serve this purpose. The general conclusion of the article “Khojaly: The Worst Massacre in the Nagorno Karabakh War and Azerbaijan’s Quest to Commemorate the Tragedy” (Karčić, 2016) is that international recognition of the Khojaly tragedy is essential for Azerbaijan both in terms of ensuring historical justice and strengthening its position in the global arena.

The Khojaly tragedy is a collective trauma not only for the direct participants and victims of the events but also for the entire Azerbaijani people. The event is assessed as a threat to national identity and cultural memory. This trauma is not only physical harm but also an attack on collective identity. The effects of the tragedy have led to profound changes in Azerbaijani society. The Khojaly incident led to a loss of a sense of security, increased distrust of political leaders, and widespread panic, spreading fear and uncertainty among a part of the population, which created social and political chaos. Rauf Garagozov, in his article published in 2010, also includes Serzh Sargsyan's⁵ statements on the Khojaly tragedy. Sargsyan stated that this incident was intended to eliminate the "delusion" of Azerbaijanis that the power of Armenian forces was small. The author presents these statements as evidence that the Armenian side deliberately demonstrated cruelty in order to create fear and panic among the population (Garagozov, 2010).

The State Commission of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Prisoners of War, Hostages and Missing Persons was established by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in order to inform the world community about the genocidal policy carried out by Armenia against the Azerbaijani people, to return to their homeland those who were captured and hostages as a result of the aggression, to increase the efficiency of the search for captured and missing and hostages in the conflict zones, and to coordinate the activities of state bodies, public and international organizations in this area. The Commission presents statistical indicators of Azerbaijani citizens who were missing and captured during the First Karabakh War and the Second Karabakh War, also known as the Homeland War. At the same time, statistical information indicating the occupied territories and the results of the occupation is also listed on the Commission's website⁶.

⁵ Serzh Azati Sargsyan (b.1954) is an Armenian politician who served as the third President of Armenia from 2008 to 2018, and twice as the Prime Minister of Armenia from 2007 to 2008 and again from 17 to 23 April 2018, when he was forced to resign in the 2018 Armenian revolution.

⁶ Human.gov.az - The State Commission of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Prisoners of War, Hostages and Missing Persons

The consequences of the IDPs and war crimes committed against the civilian population of Azerbaijan play a key role in understanding the long-term impact of the conflict and the challenges of post-war return home, and especially the difficulty of re-living together in the liberated areas. The statistics below illustrate the scale of human loss, displacement, and destruction that have shaped contemporary efforts to return to and rebuild liberated areas.

According to the State Commission on Prisoners of War, Missing and Hostages, as of 2017, 3,868 people were reported missing, and around 20,000 were killed, with 50,000 disabled as a result of the conflict. There were 350,000 refugees from Armenia and 789,000 internally displaced persons from occupied Azerbaijani territories, temporarily settled in over 1,600 locations across 62 regions. During the 44-day Second Karabakh War in 2020, 110 civilians were killed, 416 were injured, and over 4,700 residential and civilian buildings were destroyed. Additionally, 29 captives were released, while 6 servicemen went missing.⁷

These figures highlight not only the human cost of conflict but also the challenges faced in post-war recovery. The trauma of displacement, the ongoing search for missing persons, the desperate hope of soldier mothers still waiting for their missing children, and the destruction of civilian infrastructure all contribute to the experience of “returning home.” It is important for me to understand these statistics and to explore how communities in the aftermath of war try to rebuild their lives, rebuild their homes, and regain a sense of belonging. These numbers represent more than mere statistics; they reflect lives once filled with hopes and aspirations, disrupted by conflict and displacement...

3.1. The Situation after the Second Karabakh War

The Armenian Azerbaijani “Nagorno-Karabakh conflict” has gone down in history as one of the most tragic and enduring conflicts of the twentieth century, deeply affecting millions of lives. Until the peace agreement on November 10, 2020, the conflict remained one of the longest unresolved disputes, with Armenia’s long avoidance of negotiations and the passive observation of the international community, including superficial statements by the OSCE Minsk Group. Despite

⁷ The source is Human.gov.az, 2024.

sporadic escalations in 2014, 2016, and 2020, the reality of the conflict was clear. Armenia had occupied Azerbaijani territory, and Azerbaijan exercised remarkable restraint for nearly three decades, holding out hope for a peaceful resolution. According to Azerbaijani information on September 27, 2020, the offensive by Armenian armed forces prompted Azerbaijan to respond with a counter-offensive operation to restore its territorial integrity. While this is the official position of Azerbaijan, some Western narratives question the sequence of events and discuss which side initiated the conflict, and there is widespread controversy in this regard. The counter-offensive operation launched by the Armed Forces of the Republic of Azerbaijan was recorded as the largest military operation in the South Caucasus since the 1990s. The Second Karabakh War has attracted significant attention from foreign researchers and military experts due to the use of modern technology and unique warfare tactics. A notable example is the extraordinary and secret NATO meeting in Berlin, which was aimed at analyzing the results of the 44-day war. The meeting was attended by senior Pentagon officials via secure internet channels and emphasized the strategic importance of this conflict. The second half of October 2020 was a critical period, with Azerbaijani forces gaining momentum, capturing key areas such as Jabrayil, Hadrut, and Fuzuli, and advancing towards the Lachin corridor. Pashinyan's speech on October 21 called for volunteers to join the fight (Gawliczek & Iskandarov, 2021) (pages: 4-12). And of course, this war inevitably also led to mass displacement on both sides.

Armenia's long-standing dependence on Russia for security and economic support has become increasingly precarious, particularly following the Second Karabakh War in 2020. This conflict has not only highlighted the limits of Russian aid but has also demonstrated the dominance of military solutions over diplomacy, setting troubling precedents for the region. Armenia has pursued a complementary foreign policy, attempting to balance its dependence on Russia with efforts to deepen ties with the European Union and the broader West. A notable success of this approach has been Armenia's negotiation and implementation of the Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) with the EU. Armenia's increasing alignment with Europe is particularly evident in its efforts to strengthen ties with Germany, recognized as the EU's economic powerhouse, and France, which has emerged as a key geopolitical actor under President Macron. This diplomatic strategy positions Armenia as a potential bridge between the EU, Russia, and the Eurasian Economic Union. However, Armenia's post-war challenges have been further

complicated by Russia's invasion of Ukraine, which has heightened global tensions and forced Armenia to engage in a delicate balancing act. While Armenia has avoided direct involvement in the conflict and is geographically far from the war zone, it faces conflicting pressures from Russia to show loyalty and from the international community to oppose Russian aggression. Armenia's cautious approach, characterized by strategic silence and diplomatic abstentions, has so far helped it manage these demands. The aftermath of the Karabakh War and the ongoing Ukrainian conflict underscore Armenia's precarious position in regional geopolitics (Neset et al., 2023).

Between September 12 and 15, 2022, clashes erupted again on the Azerbaijan-Armenia border, marking a significant escalation in tensions. While there have been previous clashes, this latest violence occurred on the state border, not on the line of contact. The conflict was triggered by an Armenian attack on Azerbaijani forces inside Kalbajar but also highlighted Azerbaijan's concerns about its failure to implement key elements of the peace agreement brokered by Russia. Azerbaijan has particularly emphasized that Armenia should withdraw its troops from Karabakh and open communication corridors between Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan region, also known as the Zangezur Corridor. Azerbaijan claims that this corridor is not a territorial acquisition, but merely a link for free passage, similar in status to the Lachin Corridor. Furthermore, Azerbaijan's military actions were aimed at shifting Armenia's focus to border security and territorial integrity and pressuring Armenia to soften its position on the Nagorno-Karabakh issue. The situation has highlighted the fragility of peace in the region and Russia's inability or unwillingness to implement ceasefire agreements. Although Russia brokered the ceasefire, Azerbaijan claims it lasted only fifteen minutes. This further highlights the unresolved issue of border delimitation and the ongoing division over the status of Nagorno-Karabakh. Moreover, with Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the South Caucasus finds itself in an unpredictable and volatile geopolitical environment. In Armenia, Prime Minister Pashinyan is under intense pressure from his people, who are divided over peace talks with Azerbaijan. Pashinyan has called for difficult compromises, but this stance has triggered widespread protests. Armenia's request for support from the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) during the conflict has highlighted the country's dependence on Russia for security, but Russia's failure to respond to Armenia's request has fueled discontent. Azerbaijan, meanwhile, has used the changing regional power dynamics to assert itself more confidently. Russia's invasion of Ukraine has allowed Azerbaijan to strengthen its position in the region,

particularly by pressing for a peace treaty with Armenia that would recognize its sovereignty over territories such as Nagorno-Karabakh (Neset et al., 2023).

Russia has taken on a direct role on the ground for the first time by deploying around 2,000 peacekeepers to the region after the conflict. While Armenia suffered a major defeat, Azerbaijan consolidated its military and diplomatic victory. The ceasefire agreement signed on November 9-10, 2020, ended the conflict but did not bring the parties closer to an entire peace agreement. No solution was reached on the status of Nagorno-Karabakh, the root cause of the conflict, and the rights of Armenians in the region. Russia has increased its influence in the region while trying to maintain good relations with both sides. Türkiye has changed the balance in the conflict by providing military and political support to Azerbaijan. The West, especially the US and France, has been ineffective during the conflict. The end of the Russian peacekeeping force in 2025 could pose a new risk of instability. Distrust and hostility between communities make resolving the conflict even more difficult (de Waal, 2021).

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS, SELF-POSITIONING, AND METHODOLOGY

The purpose of conducting and presenting these ethnographic interviews is to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the experiences of internally displaced persons who were forcibly uprooted from their homes. Through these personal narratives, I seek to explore how individuals and families have navigated decades of displacement, how they have sustained their memories and attachments to their homeland, and how they envision and emotionally experience the prospect of return after so many years.

As part of the ethnographic component of this academic research, interviews were conducted with IDPs and their family members. In total, 12 ethnographic interviews related to this topic were carried out. The interviews were conducted with 5 male and 7 female participants. 4 of these participants were victims born into families of IDPs and who had refugee status, were born during/after the war, and spoke about their memories and the difficulties of living with refugee status. The remaining participants were live witnesses to the events themselves and IDPs who were forced to leave their homes. One of the interview participants, who is not an IDP from Karabakh, is currently a member of the academic administrative board of Karabakh University, which is involved in the Karabakh revitalization projects. A female participant who was forced to leave her home but lives not in Karabakh but in a border town in Armenia also shared her painful experiences of those days and the conflict.

Through open-ended and semi-structured interviews, I created a space where participants narrated their own experiences, memories, and interpretations without the restrictive frameworks of standardized Question-and-Answer Sessions. This allowed me to have a deeper understanding of how displacement has been experienced through the different regions, and narrated differently across generations, genders, and roles in the conflict.

Participant observation, a core ethnographic method, was unfortunately not possible due to several constraints: access to Karabakh is currently restricted for foreigners and researchers, and many IDPs remain dispersed in various locations, making sustained participant observation impractical. And being an international student also creates difficulties in accessing the specific locations

visually. In the absence of participant observation, establishing rapport and trust during interviews was crucial.

The interviews were conducted in Azerbaijani. Due to the geographical differences, the interviews were conducted online with the participants living in Azerbaijan and one person living in Türkiye. Two participants from Azerbaijan joined the study from their hometown of Lachin, having recently returned there. Three participants connected from the city of Barda, where they were settled as IDPs. One participant participated from Khankendi, where they are currently engaged in academic work, while another joined from Sumgayit, also as a displaced person. Additionally, one participant living in Antalya, Türkiye, and another currently based in Baku participated through online video calls.

Furthermore, in-person interviews were conducted with two participants born into displaced families but currently residing in Budapest, and one participant living in Nuremberg, Germany.

In total, the stories of the homes left behind by internally displaced persons from 4 (Lachin, Aghdam, Aghdara, Jabrayil) occupied regions were recorded.

Participants for the interviews were recruited via my personal network and an open call for volunteers disseminated through social media channels. All interviews were audio-recorded with approved permission. The duration of each interview varied depending on the participant, ranging from 30 minutes to 1 hour and 10 minutes. Life stories from individuals of different regions and socio-economic backgrounds were collected, each shaped by their distinct personal histories. However, one common and deeply sensitive point united them all: the experience of being forcibly displaced from their homes, living in separation for over three decades, and finding hope through memories. Interviews were arranged and conducted with participants through social networking services.

Participants were asked questions about their attachment to Karabakh, their memories, and the days they spent there, the difficulties they faced when leaving their homes, their thoughts about the war, the difficulties they experienced after the war, and their hope of return. The main goal was to listen to people's memories of their homes, how they felt away from home, and to learn what returning meant to them. The questions asked during the interview are added to the end (page 97). Of course, additional questions were asked based on the participants' answers.

4.1. Working with Traumatized Individuals and an Ethical Approach During Interviews

During the interviews, participants shared their emotional and traumatic memories related to war and displacement experiences, which created certain sensitive situations for me. Therefore, when working with traumatized individuals, I tried to apply a special approach and sensitivity, considering their emotional sensitivity.

During the interview, in cases where the participant was reluctant to answer directly or did not want to recall some memories, I directed the questions in different forms, in softer and indirect ways. At the same time, I tried to relax the interview environment and create conditions for the participant to feel freer by sometimes directing the conversation to more general or different topics.

The observation I encountered in this process was that some people try to forget what happened or convince themselves that they have forgotten. That is why, when talking about such topics, I followed the principles of paying attention to the emotional state of the participants, not forcing them, and taking breaks when necessary, during the interview.

This approach was also particularly important given the limited public discourse on war trauma and PTSD in Azerbaijan and the limited availability of psychological support. Conducting the interviews within an ethical framework and protecting the emotional well-being of the participant were among my top priorities.

4.2. The Reason Behind Choosing This Topic

I know that my choice of topic is complex, prone to controversy, and open to misunderstandings. In some parts of my research, I express my thoughts and perspectives despite the risk of being labeled a nationalist. However, I want to emphasize that my intention is not to take a nationalist stance. I consciously chose this topic with the understanding that patriotism and nationalism are different concepts.

My love and longing for Karabakh, which has existed since my childhood (despite not being from Karabakh), directed my interest toward historical sources and the decisions made on resolutions from various political perspectives during my school years. While this sentiment was instilled in me primarily by my family before school, I believe its most significant influence came from the

geography in which I grew up and the hardships I experienced because of conflicts I could not yet comprehend as a child. After all, I was raised in an ordinary family in the village of Demirchi, in the Sharur district of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, where we adapted our daily routines to a blockade regime, living with electricity borrowed from neighboring countries—one hour of power, followed by two hours of blackout. We relied on emergency generators and oil lamps kept in the house for contingencies. Growing up with the fear of the mountains—constantly reminded that the land beyond them belonged to the enemy and posed a threat—instilled trauma and fear that is difficult to put into words. But unfortunately, this was not a unique situation that applied only to me. In fact, I might even consider myself lucky in this regard. During the First Karabakh War⁸, my relatives and family members struggled to find basic food supplies such as sugar and flour, as well as medical necessities while living under blockade. They had to sustain their children with powdered milk sent from America and the Red Cross, all while going to sleep each night with the anxiety of hearing about the atrocities in Khojaly. I grew up listening to their painful memories. How could I consider myself unlucky?

I believe that the generation that grew up watching the segment titled "Blood Memory" after every news broadcast—where occupied regions of Azerbaijan were marked with a fire symbol against a backdrop of ruins and their occupation dates displayed—shares the same emotions as I do. From our earliest school years, we were all taught a slogan: "Martyrs do not die! The homeland is indivisible! (Şəhidlər ölməz! Vətən bölünməz!)" And when the list of occupation dates ended, I would always hear words that I will never forget: "The world community continues to endure this injustice..."

At the end of every national holiday or event in Azerbaijan, people would wish each other the same thing: "Inshallah, next year, we will celebrate the holiday in Karabakh." This phrase became so ingrained that, over time, it felt like just saying something that would never become a reality. I used to think that, like the elders, I too would one day listen to the melody of "Karabakh

⁸ Actually, I do not consider the events of the 1990s as a war. I believe that war is an unacceptable event conducted between two fully armed nations under fair conditions. However, in this case, we are talking about a newly established nation, deprived of its weapons and lacking an army, facing attacks from armed groups supported by a country as powerful as Russia. A historical period marked by such attacks and genocides should not be referred to as a war.

Shikastasi⁹" and hide my tears from my children. It wasn't just about electricity and gas shortages. Some mental wounds also left lasting marks on childhood memories. These include recollections that, regardless of my age, will never fade from my mind. To travel from Nakhchivan to other parts of Azerbaijan by land, we had to take what we called the "Iran route." This meant crossing the borders of the Islamic Republic of Iran, continuing along the banks of the Araz River, and then re-entering our country through the city of Bilasuvar. This was a journey we undertook every summer. What made it difficult was not changing countries, waiting in long queues at customs checkpoints under the scorching summer sun, or even the long, mountainous, and barren roads. The most painful part of the journey was looking across the Araz River towards Karabakh. Passing by the occupied regions of Zangilan, Jabrayil, and Fuzuli, seeing the destroyed and abandoned homes, witnessing the ruins of the Khudaferin Bridge, whose construction date we had memorized from history books, and, most of all, realizing that we could not set foot on those lands, was heartbreaking.

As my mother pointed to the remains of the old railway, reminiscing about how they used to travel from Baku to Nakhchivan before the war, I listened to her memories with sorrow. And as we passed through those devastating landscapes, a single question lingered in my mind: "Will I ever see Karabakh before I die?". Perhaps now, I have been able to convey, even to a small extent, what those destroyed, ghostly homes meant to me and why I chose this topic. They will rebuild those ruined houses, but will they restore their emotions? This question is at the core of my research. To find an answer, I have chosen to engage in conversations with internally displaced people and representatives of a generation that grew up under difficult conditions in displaced families, those who witnessed those painful days firsthand.

Throughout my research, I encountered not only facts I already knew but also many I did not. I want to emphasize that the challenges I faced were not only mental but also academic. The lack of scholarly articles on the concept of "home" in Azerbaijan, as well as the difficulty of obtaining precise statistical data from the First Karabakh War, significantly impacted the theoretical aspect of my study. There were moments when I came across Western sources presenting information that

⁹ Karabakh Shikastasi (Azerbaijani: Qarabağ şikəstəsi) is one of the rhythmic Azerbaijani mughams. It is a macama-based segah. Musical size - 2/4. It is performed at a heavy pace. After each verse sung by the singer, a different melody (instrumental episode) is played. It is considered one of the most popular shikeste - lyrical extended songs. Source: Wikipedia.org

contradicted what I had learned in my childhood history classes, what I had seen on the news, and even what was documented in UN resolutions. These moments of contradiction led me to question what was true and what was not. This struggle was particularly evident when I followed Western reports during the Second Karabakh War.

I fully acknowledge that war has no winners and that civilians on both sides suffer. I understand that Armenian families who left Karabakh and returned to their home country will raise children who, like me, will grow up questioning historical narratives, some of which may be censored or distorted in their schools. However, at the very least, I hope that, unlike me, they will not have to endure the hardships of basic survival. Despite the hostility instilled in us from childhood on both sides, I know that people on both sides live with hopes for a better future. I wish that in our beloved Caucasus, often described as a paradise on Earth, the threat and fear of war would finally come to an end, and that both nations could live in peace within legal frameworks.

No matter how different the upbringings, the reflected history, and the instilled faith are for the representatives of both nations, they are connected by human emotions on both sides. The emotions I approached can be reflected on the other side. Thus, Emil Sanamyan, cannot easily find an answer to the question of "to whom does Karabakh belong", considering the ownership of the region, historical context, ethnic groups, political dynamics, and at the same time the undeniable fact that Azerbaijan's claims to Karabakh are based on the principle of territorial integrity in international law and that it has been confirmed, and who dedicated his master's thesis to Karabakh in 2016 (Sanamyan, 2016), like me, also has a personal connection to the thesis. His family is an Armenian family that emigrated from Azerbaijan to America from Baku during the conflicts, and seeing Karabakh as the "home of their ancestors", shaped his understanding of the war and his perspective on peace. In this scholarly article published before the 2020 Karabakh war, Sanamyan argued that for a peaceful solution, both sides must be ready to make mutual compromises and accept past mistakes.

5. KARABAKH CONVERSATIONS - LIVED MEMORIES AND FUTURES

Before delving into the emotional and personal histories of the region, I think it is important to briefly review the statistical and demographic data that shaped life in Karabakh before the conflict. This contextual overview will provide a valuable perspective that will allow us to better understand the social dynamics, demographics, and daily realities of the region before the war changed the course of its history.

As a result of the conflict, there are 1,138,450 refugees and internally displaced persons in the country. Of these, 350,000 are Azerbaijani refugees expelled from Armenia. The number of internally displaced persons forcibly expelled from Nagorno-Karabakh and its 7 adjacent districts is a result of the military aggression of the Armenian armed forces against our country in 1988-1993 is 788,950. Between 1988 and 1992, 20,000 Azerbaijanis were killed, 100,000 were injured, and 50,000 were disabled with varying degrees of injuries. Not only were people harmed because of the conflict. But also, along with the people who suffered, they were traumatized, and lost their lives, historical and cultural monuments were also irreparably damaged. A total of 900 settlements, 150,000 houses, 7,000 public buildings, 693 schools, 855 kindergartens, 695 medical institutions, 927 libraries, 44 temples, 9 mosques, 473 historical sites, palaces and museums, 40,000 museum exhibits, 6,000 industrial and agricultural enterprises, 160 bridges and other infrastructure facilities were razed to the ground in Karabakh in 1988-1993 (State Committee for Affairs of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2025).

In contrast to the mere statistical representation of these lives and their ruined homes, this research aims to revisit this not-so-distant past through conversations with former residents of the destroyed houses. In doing so, it aims to explore how individuals narrate their experiences of home, loss, forced migration, and home in post-conflict contexts. The research question guiding this study asks how memories of displacement, exile, and the revival of hope after the Second Karabakh War shape people's sense of belonging and their dreams for the future. To capture this, I aim to present the memories shared during these encounters in three key periods: the experience of forced displacement, the years of exile, and the hope for revival after the Second Karabakh War;

contributing to anthropological discussions on memory, home, migration, and post-war reconstruction.

“I was a university student in Baku during the years of war. Within a single day, I was transformed from a student into a refugee. So many years have passed, yet I still cannot fully accept the word refugee. I refuse to internalize it, as if it were a derogatory term directed at me...” (Leyla, 2024).

These words were shared, with tearful eyes yet a smile attempting to conceal the emotion, by Leyla¹⁰, a 55-year-old woman originally from Lachin city. Having left behind painful memories, she was now speaking as a former internally displaced person who had returned, after a 30-year absence, to her home, the family house where she grew up and, as she put it, spent her childhood.

Interestingly, Leyla was not the only person who, despite the passing of 30 years, refused to identify herself with the label of “internally displaced person¹¹”. I encountered a similar sentiment during several other interviews. This widespread reluctance to accept the term piqued my interest. After all, they were not alone in their experience. However, it became evident that these individuals were not only grappling with material hardships and homelessness in the new cities they were resettled in across Azerbaijan but were also continuously burdened by the weight of the new label assigned to them—a label that carried its own form of marginalization.

For my interviewees, this marginalization manifested in daily interactions where being identified as an IDP meant being treated as socially inferior, pitied, or seen as outsiders, even after decades of living in the same communities. Leyla, in particular, expressed that she could not come to terms with the label because, to her, it reduced her identity to a single, painful episode in her life and denied her agency in rebuilding a meaningful existence afterward. Another participant similarly remarked: “*They call us ‘refugees’ even now as if we don’t belong anywhere else*”.

Events were rapidly unfolding. It was the late 1980s, and the year 1988 to be precise. Not only were tensions escalating in the Karabakh region, but Azerbaijanis living in various parts of Armenia were also experiencing a growing sense of fear and uncertainty. The looming anxiety of an imminent war was something everyone tried to dismiss from their minds, yet it was drawing

¹⁰ Names have been changed for anonymity

¹¹ In Azerbaijan most commonly used “qaçqın”, or “məcburi köçkün”.

closer with each passing day. The Sumgait events¹², which had already entered the historical record, made it clear that armed conflict was becoming inevitable.

The events that took place naturally fueled tensions and increased the risk of their escalation in places where representatives of both nations lived together. In the context of the panic that arose in the late 1980s, I met with Mrs. Khalida¹³ (70 years old), an Azerbaijani citizen who lived in Jermuk (an Armenian city on the border with the Kalbajar region of Karabakh) and left the city with her family during the unrest. During the speech, I would like to share a short excerpt from the words of a citizen who shared the panic and fear of those days:

“Jermuk was the town where my late husband was born, raised, and lived with his entire family. His grandfather, Ali Bey, was originally born in what is now the territory of Armenia. Due to internal family conflicts, he left his hometown and relocated his family to this mountainous town, which, at the time, was a sparsely populated border settlement. He used to recount that when they first settled there, around the 1910s, no other families had moved to the area yet, as it was considered remote and isolated. Over time, Armenians also began to settle in the town, and it gradually grew. Life in such a close-knit community, where all our relatives lived together, was peaceful and comfortable. I myself worked as a nurse at the local hospital. By then, I had already given birth to two children, and to this day, their birth certificates list their place of birth as Armenia. In our family, everyone spoke Armenian fluently. Many Armenians also spoke our language. In fact, when conversations took place in Russian, some would grow irritated and insist that we speak in Turkish, they referred to us as Turks, and to our language as the Turkish language...Both communities lived together in relative harmony until the events of the 1980s disrupted this coexistence. At that time, public demonstrations began, and slogans such as “**Gharabaghy mern e**” (translated from Armenian as "Karabakh is ours") echoed in the streets. Naturally, we felt anxious and afraid”.

¹² On February 27-29, 1988, clashes and mass riots broke out between Armenians and Azerbaijanis in Sumgayit. 32 people (26 Armenians, 6 of other nationalities) were killed, more than 400 people were injured, more than 200 apartments and more than 50 objects were destroyed, and the state suffered 7 million rubles in damage. The victims were mainly Armenians living in Sumgayit and other civilians. At that time, more than 18 thousand Armenians lived in the city, and the vast majority of them were protected and rescued by their Azerbaijani neighbors. One of the main organizers of the events was Eduard Grigoryan, of Armenian origin, but he was protected by the USSR Prosecutor General's Office and evaded responsibility. Official investigations proved that the Sumgayit events were a political provocation organized by the USSR State Security Committee (KGB). The goal was to separate Nagorno-Karabakh from Azerbaijan and create the basis for an international information campaign. The incident was planned by taking advantage of the socio-economic difficulties in Sumgayit and the presence of refugees expelled from Armenia.

¹³ Interview date: 2nd of April 2025, Sumgayit/Azerbaijan.

At this point, a question arose in my mind: *Karabakh*? After the occupation, the region's name was changed and declared as the so-called “Republic of Artsakh” by Armenians, who claimed that these lands were historically their ancient territory known as Artsakh¹⁴. How was it that, during those protests, it was still being referred to as “Karabakh?” The response to my question was as follows:

“At that time, the word ‘Artsakh’ wasn’t used at all. Everywhere, in the streets, during the protests, it was still called ‘Karabakh’. Even the Armenians were calling it Karabakh back then” (Khalida, 2025).

“Following those events, the Sumgayit incident marked the peak of the tensions. Out of fear, we gathered a few belongings and important documents during the night and fled to Nakhchivan, to my family’s home. After staying there for a few days, we moved to Sumgayit. Here, we exchanged our house in Jermuk with an Armenian family. I remember my son; he was just three years old at the time. Whenever he saw people gathering in the street, thinking it was another protest, he would lean out of the window and shout the slogan he had memorized without understanding its meaning: “*Gharabaghy mern e!*” ...”

At this stage, the interview took a different turn. The experiences and historical facts that were never officially announced started to surface. There are some incidents in history for which official sources hold no records, but this does not erase the fact that these events indeed took place. This was one of those moments.

Although I could not find official documentation regarding this particular fact, through oral histories and family narratives, it became evident that even before the Karabakh War had fully erupted, during the initial outbreaks of tension, many families, from both ethnicities, began predicting the possibility of an unavoidable conflict. Consequently, Azerbaijani families living in Armenia and Armenian families living in Azerbaijan started contacting one another through acquaintances to exchange their homes before the situation worsened.

As narrated by Khalida, her family also exchanged their home with an Armenian family living in Sumgayit. She recalls that at that time, they went to what was known as the “*Evlər İdarəsi*” (Housing Department) and officially registered the exchanged properties.

¹⁴ Artsakh, officially the Republic of Artsakh or the Republic of Nagorno-Karabakh, was a breakaway state in the South Caucasus whose territory was internationally recognized as part of Azerbaijan.
Source: Wikipedia.org.

"We left just in time-right after the Sumgait events began. My sister-in-law's family, however, still believed that the situation would calm down and refused to leave their home. But while they were away one day, their house in Jermuk was set on fire, and all their belongings were destroyed. It wasn't just them; other Azerbaijani families who had also chosen not to leave were harassed, their doors and windows were broken, and they were openly threatened to abandon the city" (Khalida, 2025).

Of course, it wasn't only the houses that were being exchanged - identities and lives were also being reshaped. Armenian women married to Azerbaijani men, sensing the growing hostility around them, began changing their names in official documents to avoid attracting aggression before the conflict fully escalated. Khalida shared a personal example: her brother-in-law's wife, Alyona, who was one of the Armenians living in Baku, changed her name to Lala during those turbulent times. Currently, since her family has returned to Armenia, she occasionally meets her relatives in Georgia. Because it is not possible to travel between Azerbaijan and Armenia.

Khalida also explained how, despite familial ties being maintained to some extent, social fears remained deeply entrenched. When another brother-in-law's son became a martyr during the Second Karabakh War, Alyona, whose Armenian origin was known to the entire extended family, did not attend the mourning ceremony, fearing potential protests or backlash, even from within the family circle. When asked how she perceived the situation, Khalida admitted to feeling a mix of sadness and understanding. She described Lala's decision as "*unavoidable under the circumstances*". Despite the historical and societal tensions, Khalida stated that she still felt close to Lala and respected her for the difficult choices she had to make. Although the mourning event revealed lingering societal fears, Khalida emphasized that people would have supported Lala's presence had she chosen to come.

5.1. Conflict Turned into War (1988-1994)

These crises, which began in the late 1980s, were an indication that a major conflict was imminent. Events became even more serious after both countries declared their independence¹⁵ after leaving the Soviet Union.

Since the escalation of the conflict, and especially since the First Karabakh War, the borders between Armenia and Azerbaijan have remained closed, making direct travel between the two countries impossible for ordinary citizens. This ongoing situation has not only deepened the separation of communities but has also made it impossible for displaced individuals and families to visit their former homes, cemeteries, or relatives on the other side of the border. This context is crucial to understanding the significance of the memories and narratives shared by those affected.

As shown in Table 6, with the arrival of the 1990s, although only two villages were initially occupied, the escalating conflict led to the first major occupation after both countries gained independence. This occurred towards the end of 1991 (on December 28) with the seizure of Khankendi. The subsequent massacre committed in Khojaly intensified fear among the population. These acts of violence, aimed at forcing people to abandon their homes, tragically revealed how the situation was deteriorating into a humanitarian catastrophe. Yet, despite these events, many residents in other regions were still reluctant to leave their homes. As the occupation of regions continued one by one, the next victims became the residents of Lachin.

5.2. From Village to Ruins: The Loss of Homeland

I would also like to include excerpts from the memoirs of sisters Leyla (55, pseudonym) and Lamiya (56, pseudonym), who were forced to leave their hometown of Lachin. Their memoirs not only provide personal accounts of displacement but also provide valuable insights into how people experience and narrate the loss of place, home, and identity. This section contributes to anthropological discussions on the emotional and material dimensions of displacement, showing how attachments to home are constructed and transformed into situations of displacement. In their stories, we move from the larger image of a lost village to the intimate space of a destroyed family

¹⁵ Armenia got independence - 23 September 1991, Azerbaijan - 18 October 1991.

home, and then to the single ancient tree standing in their yard – a silent witness to their past. These memoirs reflect that places are not only physical locations, but also full of meaning, history, and belonging. By listening to these details, the sisters' stories reveal how displaced people connect with lost homes through memories and material symbols that anthropologists have long considered important in the process of domestication in exile and in imagining possible futures after conflict and loss.

"Karabakh is our wounded place. One's homeland begins from the place where they were born and raised. No matter where life takes you, that place remains the dearest to your heart. I was born in Lachin, and I went to kindergarten and school there. When I was a university student, we lost our land, and for 30 years I longed to return. Only after losing it did we truly realize how beautiful a place we had lived in. Wherever we went, we would search for it, unconsciously comparing every mountain and school building we saw to our own, hoping to find something that resembled our home..." (Leyla, 2025).

These words were Leyla's expression of her deep emotional attachment to Karabakh and the importance of place in shaping a sense of belonging and identity. The act of searching for familiar figures in unfamiliar landscapes shows how displaced people carry their homes with them in their memories and dreams.

This deep sense of loss and constant longing was also evident in the memories of her sister Lamiya. She spoke of how the old tree in her family's yard remained a symbol of their former yard. Like Leyla's reflection on her village, Lamiya's memory emphasizes how personal objects and places, however ordinary, become distinct memories of memory and identity after displacement.

"After the occupation of Shusha on May 8¹⁶, the situation in Lachin became even more critical. The surrounding highlands fell under Armenian control, and from those positions, they began shelling Lachin. There were instances where multiple civilians-five or six people-were killed simultaneously in the town center by rocket attacks. Residential houses were also targeted. Although it did not escalate into a massacre like the one in Khojaly, the situation forced people to leave the town. On May 18, Lachin was completely taken over by Armenian forces. At that time, my sister and I were university students in Baku, and my parents were among the last families to leave the town. Given the fear that had spread after the events in Khojaly, on May 18, they were compelled to abandon their home" (Leyla, 2025).

¹⁶ Occupation year of Shusha city – 1992.

As she recounted her memories of Lachin, a folk song with Lachin in it, and the idea that it belonged to the city, played in my head. When Leyla recounted her memories of Lachin, a folk song that I had heard since childhood and that had been etched in my memory, it came to mind. This song is known as “Ay Lachin” and is one of the oldest folk songs dedicated to the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan, especially Lachin. Although the exact date of its creation is unknown, and it has even been claimed that it was written for a girl named Lachin, it has been passed down from generation to generation and has survived to this day. For me, this song is not just a melody; it carries the pain of being separated from one’s homeland, one’s native land, the pain of being homeless, being expelled, and at the same time, the hope of returning every time I listen to it. It evokes the same emotions for many people in Azerbaijan who listen to this song: on the one hand, a deep attachment to Lachin and Karabakh, and on the other hand, the anguish of loss.

*Araz flows with silt,
With bunches and bunches of flowers.
I love my beloved,
With sweet-sweet words.
Ay Lachin, dear Lachin,
I sacrifice myself to you, Lachin.¹⁷*

The emotional connection to this land was not only evident in physical migration, but also within the city.

“Although I have not been in an IDP camp, I have been living in Baku since my family moved from Lachin. My family and I have our own house here, but when I mention home, I still mean this house in Lachin. All my childhood memories, my youth come to mind” (Leyla, 2024).

¹⁷ Original in Azerbaijani:
Araz axar lil ilə,
Dəstə-dəstə gül ilə.
Mən yarımı sevrəm,
Şirin-şirin söz ilə.
Ay Laçın, can Laçın,
Mən sənə qurban Laçın.

Leyla Khanum (an honorific title for women in Azerbaijani culture) has already returned to her home in Lachin. During our online video conversation, she spoke about that house where the very one where she was born and raised. After her family was forced to leave, the house was occupied by an Armenian family. Following the recent war, the house was renovated and officially returned to them. Although the structure of the house remained the same, she mentioned with sorrow that many of the trees in the yard had been destroyed. She recalled the joy she felt upon finding a single old surviving tree from her childhood. She described how seeing the one remaining tree made her feel happy, although it had grown and changed over time. In her memory, however, the image of the tree remained as it once was, just as she had left it.

Not only in this account, but in many other conversations as well, what seemed to distress people the most was not only the destruction of their homes, but perhaps even more painfully, the loss of the trees. As Leyla Khanum sorrowfully expressed: *“We can somehow understand the houses, they were left behind and destroyed. But what did they want from the trees? What was their fault?”*.

As she spoke from her veranda, with the lush green mountains of Lachin¹⁸ visible in the background, the happiness in her eyes was unmistakable, though she could not entirely hide the tears that welled up while recounting painful memories. After all, it was the end of a 30-year-long yearning.

On June 28, 2024, Leyla Khanum and her family officially received the keys to their newly restored home. Although she currently works as a schoolteacher in Baku and can only visit Lachin during the summer holidays, she expressed her sincere hope to move back permanently as soon as possible.

¹⁸ By the joint statement signed by the President of Azerbaijan, the President of Russia, and the Prime Minister of Armenia on November 10, the evacuation of territories by Armenia was carried out according to a schedule. According to that schedule, the Lachin district was also liberated from Armenian occupation on December 1. It should be noted that Lachin is one of the 7 districts located around Nagorno-Karabakh. Source: Lachin District Executive Power of the Republic of Azerbaijan, <http://lachin-ih.gov.az/>

Photo 2: Mammadovs' Family House in Lachin City, Construction time June 2022. Source: Personal archive of Mrs. Leyla, June 2024

Leyla Khanum's sister, Lamiya Khanum, who shared both the same childhood home and the experience of displacement, recalled her memories in the following way:

“The last time I was in Lachin was in March 1992. As I was a university student at the time, I was not among the family members who were forcibly displaced during the occupation. At that time, districts were falling one after another, yet we still believed that Lachin would remain ours and would not be occupied. It was only when my father and other relatives arrived in Baku that we understood Lachin had also been taken. Therefore, when I returned to Lachin 30 years later, in 2022, it felt as though I was coming back home after a long vacation. A very long vacation” (Lamiya,2025).

This last sentence particularly caught my attention because it marks a long period of displacement as if it were a temporary break, a long vacation. This expression is an indication of the attachment of a person to their native land and the fact that this attachment is not dependent on the limitations of time and space. From an anthropological perspective, such metaphors show us how the concept of "home" is preserved in people's memory and thoughts, and how the connection with this land continues even when they are far away. The expression "long vacation" is an approach that both softens the weight of the trauma and keeps the hope, the certainty that she will return, within it. It is as if she never completely lost her native land but stayed away for a while. It also tries to tell us how living with loss and the thought of perhaps returning to that home in the future holds a special place in human memory.

At the time, the difficulty in transmitting information and maintaining regular contact with others contributed to increased levels of fear and anxiety among people. As Lamiya noted in her account, *"We did not know who was alive and what had happened to whom, and this uncertainty deeply unsettled us"*. She also recalled, with tears in her eyes, the nights she could not sleep after hearing about the atrocities committed during the Khojaly massacre (see footnote 3).

“One morning you wake up to find that you have lost your memories, your native town, and your childhood home, and you realize that it is not only your house you have lost, but also your classmates, your friends, your relatives, and even the graves of your ancestors, which were sacred to you. It felt like a nightmare. There were times when I thought it was just a dream, and that I would soon wake up in our old house. Starting life from scratch felt unbearably difficult. I know families who, when they first arrived as internally displaced persons, had absolutely nothing, not even a glass for drinking water. Although people have now managed to rebuild their lives in the places they were resettled, everyone still longs to return to their hometowns, to their ancestral lands.

We managed to take very few belongings from our house in Lachin. When vehicles arrived to evacuate people, my father prioritized going to remote villages to collect vulnerable elderly people and families with children. As a result, we left with almost nothing, carrying instead what was more precious, lives. Since then, no belongings have been retrieved from our home; we only managed to take some clothes. The first time I returned to our house before its renovation in 2022, I could not stop crying throughout the entire journey. Passing through Jabrayil, the destruction was so severe that it no longer felt like a town but rather a graveyard; the atmosphere in those places was unbearably heavy. When we arrived at our own house, I could hardly recognize it. The people who had occupied it had ruined it to such a degree that nothing remained the same. We used to have more than twenty fruit trees in our garden, but only one had survived" (Lamiya, 2024).

Lamiya Khanum recalled that everything inside the house had been destroyed, and all the belongings had been removed. The only remaining object from her childhood was an old swing in the yard. Although it was eventually taken down by the authorities due to its worn condition, seeing it during her first visit back filled her with a deep sense of nostalgia and unexpected happiness. It was, as she described, a small but precious connection to the life they once had in Lachin. For Lamiya, the swing was not just a childhood memory. It was also a painful symbol of coming to terms with the loss of her entire family and village. Such return visits show us how traumatic experiences with space leave their mark on memory. Seeing her home destroyed and only having a swing left behind is both nostalgic and deeply sad.

“For me, war means the tears of mothers. It means lives left incomplete. That is why I don’t want to think about war — I feel as if, should I think of it, it might happen again” (Leyla, 2025).

While speaking with me through a video call from her long-awaited home in Lachin, Lamiya Khanum shared her memories:

“Sometimes, when I sit here, I feel like I can still hear the voices of our childhood, our laughter and games. When I walk into the kitchen, it feels like my mother is there, cooking something for us. A land only becomes a homeland when it has a home on it. That’s why both the home and the homeland must be protected. I feel much closer and more connected to our house in Lachin. Even when I was in our house in Baku, I always felt like a stranger there. It wasn’t truly mine. But now that I’ve returned here, even our house in Baku has started to feel familiar to me. Before, I felt like we didn’t have a home of our own, but now this place makes even that home feel like it belongs. I work in a hospital in Baku. Here in Lachin, the hospital hasn’t opened yet, but I hope once it’s ready, I can work here and stay. I don’t want to leave this place again (laughing)” (Lamiya, 2024).

From the words and emotions of both sisters who have returned to their childhood home, it becomes clear that the issue is not merely about having a house or being able to purchase one. Although both Leyla Khanum live in Baku with their families and Lamiya Khanum has her own separate house there, they have rediscovered the feeling of “home” in their house in Lachin. The sense of belonging, the ability to return freely whenever they wish, and the lifting of restrictions and longing have even made their current homes in Baku feel more familiar and emotionally connected to them. Both women openly expressed their desire to move back and continue their lives in Lachin. What makes this issue particularly interesting is how the rest of the family, especially the younger generation who were not born in Karabakh and did not experience those memories firsthand, but only through stories, perceive this return. To better understand this, I also interviewed with Leyla Khanum’s daughter, Selcan¹⁹ (26 years old).

Selcan, born in Baku in 1998, completed both her school and university education in the capital. Although she had never seen Karabakh before and did not grow up in the family’s ancestral home, she inherited a strong sense of connection to the region through the stories and emotions shared

¹⁹ Interview date: 4th of August 2024, Baku/Azerbaijan.

by her parents. Describing her first visit²⁰ to Lachin, she expressed her emotions in these words: *“Before going, I felt as if I was traveling to a foreign place. But once I arrived, it was as though I had reunited with loved ones I hadn’t seen for many years. It felt like finding a blood relative I had lost. It was a magnificent feeling.”*

Although Selcan did not personally experience the hardships of displacement, as she was born in Baku within a displaced family, the memories and narratives shared by her family left a lasting mark on her sense of identity. She benefited from state-supported higher education as a registered internally displaced person, yet the deeper connection to Lachin came through intergenerational storytelling. From an early age, Selcan recalls hearing frequent stories about their ancestral home in Lachin from her maternal relatives. She emphasized that before ever visiting the house, she already had a mental map of what it would be like, where each flower was planted, and what every corner of the home once looked like. During their first return to the house, witnessing her mother and grandparents bursting into tears was an unfamiliar emotional moment for her. However, she noted that by imagining how it would feel to lose her own home in Baku, she was able to empathize with their pain and longing. Through this reflective empathy, she gained a deeper understanding of the emotional weight carried by her family’s displacement.

It becomes clear that just as material cultural heritage and memories are passed down from generation to generation, traumas are also passed down from generation to generation as a collective trauma. This is once again witnessed when speaking with Selcan. This also shows that for the post-war generation like Selcan, these issues were not just history or parental trauma, but also a process of forming their own identity and understanding their sense of belonging.

"For me, home is the place where I feel completely safe and comfortable. I love Baku immensely and believe that no place in the world can ever feel as familiar to me as Baku does. Even if all my comforts were taken away, I would not want to leave Baku. I used to think that I could never feel connected to Lachin, but the reality turned out to be the opposite. I also felt comfortable and at home there, and now I can say that both places hold the meaning of 'home' for me. I will always travel there for visits, but no matter how much

²⁰ 29th of June 2024. According to Selcan, during their first return, the belongings being moved were transported by the government. However, they chose to travel with their own private car, even though the government also offered to arrange their transportation. The journey took approximately 5 to 6 hours.

the city is developed, and modern conveniences are established, I do not plan to move there permanently" (Selcan, 2024).

Attachment to place is not solely determined by being born or having lived in a location for a long time, but is also deeply connected to feelings of emotional safety and comfort. Although Selcan initially perceived Lachin as an unfamiliar place in her mind, experiencing a sense of belonging upon her arrival there was unexpected for her. This illustrates how powerful and inherited emotional memory related to place can be. However, despite this emotional connection, Selcan does not wish to leave behind her urban identity and the conveniences of city life. Attachment to a place is not only determined by being born there or living there for a long time. This attachment is also closely related to emotional security, a sense of belonging, and a memory passed down from generation to generation. Although Selcan previously imagined Lachin as a foreign and distant place in her memory, when she went there, he was surprised to find himself unexpectedly close to it. This shows how strong and hereditary emotional memory and attachment to one's roots can be. This sense of belonging and security was especially important to Selcan. Because some of her displaced relatives like her were never able to relive this feeling. However, despite all this emotional attachment, Selcan does not want to give up the identity formed in the urban environment and the comfort provided by city life. This shows, on the one hand, the rebirth of the sense of attachment to one's native land and roots, and on the other hand, the desire to preserve the new identity that city life has shaped in a person over many years. Even though Karabakh is being redeveloped, at this stage, she does not consider giving up Baku for permanent residence there. But she also noted that if her parents sought help and wished to relocate, she would support their decision to move. This demonstrates that, while the sense of attachment and belonging can be strong, for the younger generation, leaving behind the familiar environment in which they were raised is not easily embraced. To observe this dynamic more closely, the perspectives of other young participants from different cities will be documented in the following sections.

5.3. Ongoing Occupations, Those Who Left Their Homes - Aghdara

The dates showed the summer of 1993. The months passed quickly, yet the situation remained unchanged. Azerbaijan was losing its cities one by one. With each passing day, anxiety grew among the people, as news of neighbouring regions being captured spread. People lived in a

constant dilemma, torn between the fear that their turn would come next and the hope that their own homes would somehow be spared.

To better understand what it felt like in those moments, when war was ongoing and the sound of weapons had already reached one's doorstep, and to hear what life was like in the city of Aghdara during those days. I conducted both online and face-to-face interviews with the Malikov (pseudonym) family, who were forcibly displaced from their home in Aghdara. The family consists of a father (Mr. Kamal, 62)²¹, a mother (Mrs. Sura, 56)²², and their son (Tahir, 28)²³, who was born after the war. Through these conversations, I closely learned about their painful memories and their personal perspectives on the concept of return. Although each family member shared different memories and personal narratives shaped by their individual experiences, there was one common identity that connected them all: that of an "internally displaced person". The Malikov family, who were already eager to return, recalled those days as follows:

"My parents and I were born and raised in the Aghdara district. I lived in Aghdara even after we got married. Before, when we were newly married, we lived with my family, and my house was under construction. We were planning to move as soon as our house was ready before spring, but it so happened that on May 12, we were forced to leave not only our house, but even Aghdara, where I was born and raised, behind us" (Kamal, 2025).

People not only left behind the homes they had lived in and built memories within, but they also abandoned the homes where future hopes, joys, and yet-to-be-lived memories were meant to unfold. As Mr. Kamal poignantly expressed, "*we were never fated to live in our newly built house...*".

"When we first arrived in Barda, we went to my in-laws' house (her husband was from Barda and her parents lived there). Then we lived in a tent for about 3 months. The tents were organized by the state. It was in the form of a settlement, called a Turkish settlement, an Arab settlement. They were aid tents from those countries. I don't remember exactly which Arab country it was, but it was called an Arab settlement. We lived in a tent that I bought on my own. The situation in the tents in the settlement was more difficult. When it rained, the situation was very bad. After the ceasefire in 1995, the settlements began to be built. The conditions in the tents set up in those relief camps were much worse. The

²¹ Interview date: 20th of May 2025, Barda, Azerbaijan. Online videocall.

²² Interview date: 30th of March 2025, Barda, Azerbaijan. Online videocall.

²³ Interview date: 21st of January 2025, Nuremberg, Germany.

conditions in the tents we set up with our resources were much better than those” (Kamal, 2025).

Mr. Kamal, who was himself a war veteran, volunteered to serve in the war between 1988 and 1994. He also lost his loved ones in the war, which he sees as a period with bitter memories of the loss of young people. The tone of his voice that faltered when he mentioned that his aunt's husband and cousin had been martyred during the war was actually a symbol of the tears that had flowed inside him. In Azerbaijani culture, men hiding their tears is a scene that I am very familiar with. But at the same time, the pride he felt when mentioning the name and surname of his relative who had been martyred and earned the title of National Hero was also reflected on his face. Speaking about his memories as a war participant, he noted that the 366th regiment, a Russian military unit stationed in Khankendi after the city was occupied, actively supported the Armenian forces. According to him, the main equipment and military support were provided by the Russians to the opposing side. He also noted that the newly independent Azerbaijani state did not have a military force at the beginning of the war and could not receive support from other states. Towards the end of the war, old and small weapons were provided to them by the Azerbaijani state.

“The fighting began in February. In March, from the night of the 11th to the 12th, the fighting continued non-stop until the morning. They were bombing the city. The women and the elderly left the city a little earlier, while the men continued to fight. But on March 12, our village was completely evacuated” (Kamal, 2025).

Mr. Kamal, who had the chance to see his home again after a long time of longing, said that he planned to go again soon after he went for the first time in March 2025. Although the view he saw was not very pleasant, seeing that other villages were being renovated by the government one by one, means that he will soon be able to return to his home. Mr. Kamal, who found this development fast and gratifying, also said that he was looking forward to the day when he would return to Aghdere after the renovation.

“I went to our house in Aghdara, and nothing was left. You could tell from the stones that there had once been a house here. But 95% of the houses there were destroyed. Now we have a house in Barda, where we live. Armenians did not live in our houses after the war. Before the war, they lived in the center of Aghdara. They called Aghdara Mardaket (in Armenian). I would say that the village where the most Armenians lived was Aghdara. They could also speak Azerbaijani. In the neighboring village next to us, there were

Armenians who spoke Azerbaijani, and some Azerbaijanis could also speak Armenian. At first, we lived in peace, until the war” (Kamal, 2025).

This interview fragment shows not only the destruction of houses and forced displacement, but also how the multi-ethnic village life existed before the war. Azerbaijanis and Armenians lived together in the village, knowing each other's language. However, when the conflict began, these relationships completely broke down, and the villages became ethnically divided and devastated places.

5.4. Is It Possible to Live Together After War?

After Mr. Kamal's words that we lived in peace before the war in his speech, I had asked him, just as asked all the participants, how they felt about living together with the Armenians again. Of course, the answer I received was not positive. Although he noted that during the war, those fighting on the other side were Armenians from Yerevan and other regions of Armenia, and that the majority of Karabakh Armenians did not participate in the war, after all that had happened, he did not look favorably on the two nations living together as before. Interestingly, although he mentioned that they lived well together before the war, Mr. Kamal was not the only one who expressed his unwillingness to live together with that nation. All the participants mentioned above did not look favorably on this issue. This includes even Khalida Khanum, who lived in the city of Jermukh in Armenia before the war. The young people's reaction to this must be due to the period of education they received and the aggression they felt from their families, which is why young people are able to express their unwillingness on this issue more firmly. Leyla Khanum noted that she believes that this experience is not completely impossible, since they lived peacefully side by side with Armenians many years ago. In her opinion, the distrust and hostility between them may last for many years, but Armenians who are not victims of the war and want to live here should be allowed to live. According to her, these people have already gotten used to these lands and these conditions, and it is not right to put pressure on them. She added that although relations are not as cordial as before, it is possible to live side by side with a certain distance.

Of course, the fear of living together brings back painful memories of the past and a sense of danger at every moment, so I think this might ease gradually for them over time. To be honest, to empathize with how they might feel when confronted with this question, I posed the same question

to myself. And it seems evident that answering such a question is not as easy as it might appear. On one hand, there is a history marked by difficult events, painful memories, longing for the homeland, the loss of loved ones, and the memory of those who were martyred. On the other hand, when one considers that these two peoples once lived together, that we remain neighboring states, and that, while genuine neighborly relations may not be fully restored, it is nevertheless necessary for both nations to find ways to coexist in the same geography, at least by reducing hatred and embracing a more humane and tolerant framework.

But I understand that this is just as difficult now as it was when we lost our lands. Because now those who suffered from the war are on the other side, and their hatred is likely to grow even more. That is why it is so difficult for me to imagine the idea of two peoples living in peace with open borders as before. Future generations may witness this. But I do not think that our generation will be able to see it today.

5.5. A Family's Journey Through Displacement: Sura Khanum's Perspective

I try to understand the hardships of being displaced from the place you were born and raised, the place you call home, even if only a little, from the internally displaced persons I spoke to, but how does Sura Khanum, who, despite not being born there, is eagerly awaiting her new home where she went as a bride, starting a family with different hopes and dreams, see the life of a refugee, returning to her hometown of Barda as an internally displaced person? To evaluate the sense of belonging and home in this context, a meeting was held with Mr. Kamal Bey's wife, Sura Khanum (56 years old).

“We were in the process of building our house during the war; the conflict had already started by 1988, the year we got married. Before we could move into the completed house, we were forced to leave Aghdara. We had to abandon the construction and leave. It was in March 1991 when we had no other choice but to leave. I left earlier than my husband, as the clashes and shootings had intensified. Although the conflict began in 1988, at that time it did not feel like a full-scale war. We could not have anticipated that it would escalate to such an extent. Around a year after I left, it intensified drastically. I remember the day before I left in 1991, our village lost 18 martyrs in a single day. It was then that we understood that the situation had become critical. At that time, I had two very young

children; one was one year and six months old, and the other was just forty days old. Fearing for their safety, we decided to leave” (Sura, 2025).

Sura Khanum noted that the house they left behind belonged to her husband's parents, and she recalled how difficult and unwillingly she had to leave it. She shared that after leaving, she fell into depression. Although they initially tried to live in a tent because her children were very young, the harsh conditions eventually forced them to move into more sheltered homes. While recounting those painful memories, the emotions evoked by those difficult days were reflected in me during our conversation.

Like the records of other IDPs, the first heads mentioned that they only received small amounts of aid from the state, such as flour, pasta, oil, and oil (as petrol), and after these aids ended, they received a small amount of financial aid allocated per person. One of the most difficult aspects of the life of an internally displaced person was waiting in line for hours to receive food assistance. The experiences of standing in line for hours to receive aid and living in tents act as symbolic elements of both makeshift homemaking and the period of mourning for the lost home in the lives of IDPs. This experience, as in the first interviewee, creates a different and deeper emotional impression than for those who have not experienced physical suffering and real loss. Here you can compare and analyze these two different experiences of IDPs. It was also a fact confirmed by all participants that most of the aid came from foreign countries. Although the interviewees could not always specify the countries, historical records indicate that Türkiye, Saudi Arabia, and other Muslim countries, as well as international organizations, provided significant humanitarian assistance during that period.

The level of assistance provided indeed varied depending on the location and time of the IDPs. The situation was more difficult during the first mass arrivals. Later, after the ceasefire was declared (1994), the situation gradually began to be brought under control. However, it would not be right to expect a newly formed state to initially perfectly accommodate more than 1 million IDPs with ease.

“Those days were very difficult days, my daughter. Those days left an indelible scar. It is impossible to forget. During the first war, there was no shelling of Barda, but during the second war, they were shelling Barda, civilian areas. These events made us relive the horror of that bloody first war” (Sura, 2025).

This note from Sura Khanum brought me back to the night of October 17, 2020. It was past 1 am when the news and live broadcasts showed the city of Ganja. Civilian houses were being hit, and lives were being pulled out from under the rubble. And that scene that I will never forget, the lifeless hand of a baby being pulled out. While watching these events live, it is impossible for me to forget the words of the Turkish journalist lady crying, "*The child's hand touched mine, it was like ice.*" That event caused such a deep shock in me that even though I was in Baku, I felt in danger. I slept with an emergency bag that I had prepared like an earthquake bag next to me at night in case the building we lived in was hit. The only thing I thought about was how to save my cat, who was sleeping in different places at night, if such an incident happened.

I believe it is important to present several pieces of information as factual concerning these points:

Human Rights Watch reported²⁴ that during the September-November 2020 conflict²⁵, Armenian forces carried out unlawful rocket and artillery attacks targeting civilian areas in Azerbaijan, resulting in significant destruction and casualties. Approximately 40,000 people were internally displaced, with dozens of civilians killed and hundreds injured²⁶. Notably, ballistic missile strikes on Ganja and Barda caused severe damage to residential neighborhoods, hospitals, and other civilian infrastructure, violating the laws of war (Human Rights Watch, 2020).

When returning to the interview with Mrs. Sura, I noticed that whenever she spoke about the village of Sirkhavand in the Aghdara district, she always referred to it as "our village." Having lived there for just over three years, Mrs. Sura feels a deep connection to the village with her house of un-lived memories, considering it her own and belonging to it. She expressed her eager anticipation to return to their home, which she had long planned to do, but was unable to do so.

²⁴ Human Rights Watch documented 11 incidents of ballistic missiles, unguided artillery rockets, and large-caliber shells landing in residential areas between September and November 2020. In four cases, civilian targets were hit despite the absence of nearby military facilities. Hugh Williamson, HRW's Europe and Central Asia director, emphasized repeated violations of the laws of war by Armenian forces.

²⁵ On October 17, ballistic missile strikes (including Scud-B and Smerch missiles) hit two residential neighbourhoods in Ganja, killing 21 civilians and injuring 5. The missiles caused widespread destruction of houses and civilian casualties. Due to their inaccuracy and wide destructive radius, these attacks are considered violations of international humanitarian law.

²⁶ On October 28, an attack on Barda damaged the Treatment and Diagnostic Center, the Migration Service, and the sports complex, killing 21 civilians and injuring over 70. Cluster bombs and Smerch missiles were reportedly used, affecting medical staff and patients.

On November 7, a rocket attack shelled the village of Araz, killing a 16-year-old child. There were no military targets nearby, and the Armenian side failed to issue effective warnings to civilians, making the attack particularly egregious.

Sura Khanum, who said that she has lived in Barda for more than 30 years and feels at home here, but still wants to return there, said:

"My daughter, you are now far from the country, from your homeland; you know what it feels like to be a stranger. We felt the same way. It was very painful for us when others called us refugees and excluded us. Thankfully, this longing has finally ended".

I would like to highlight the thoughts of the family, the generation that left their homes, about returning and their longing for home, as well as the different approaches between generations, as well as how the parents and their child/ son, born after the war (1997), think about this issue. Although I first contacted Tahir through mutual acquaintances and later met his parents and heard from Tahir about the painful journey their family had gone through, it was important for me to listen to the different approaches of both generations. Because what the older generation does not always mention or see in meetings has a different meaning for the new generation, and although some painful memories are hidden by the elders in order to forget, this is less common in the younger generation. I witnessed this again during the conversations I had with his family after talking to Tahir.

"I have heard about Karabakh from my family since childhood — how life was there, what our house was like. There are no photographs; I could only imagine what kind of home we might have had based on their stories. However, I believe that if my parents had not spoken about Karabakh, if my father had not been from Karabakh, I would not have felt any emotional connection to it, because it was a place I had never seen" (Tahir, 2025).

We see Tahir feel a connection to Karabakh through the stories he heard from his family since childhood. This is an example of how IDPs use storytelling to create a connection to belonging and roots, as we mentioned earlier.

After Aghdara was divided between three districts (see footnote 2 for details), Tahir, who was officially registered as an internally displaced person in Aghdam district, grew up longing for the home he had only heard about from his family's memories. Interestingly, rather than focusing on the war and their forced displacement, his family chose to share stories of their lives before the conflict, how beautiful nature was, and how peaceful the days had been. This illustrates how, despite their pain, the family sought to preserve and pass down the memory of good times, instilling hope and a sense of belonging in the new generation.

“I have been living in Germany for 5-6 years now, but when I think of home, that house in Azerbaijan, the house where my family lives, comes to mind. I feel more comfortable there. I see home as a place that brings together those I love. Since childhood, we have moved a lot. We have lived in many houses. When I was 8 years old, we bought a house for ourselves. Until then, we lived in a tent, a wagon, and rented houses. But the one that remains in my memory the most was the 3-room wagon (railway carriage) we lived in. When I still go to Barda, I go and look in front of it. My childhood and the difficulties we went through come to mind. Of course, for me now, wherever my family is, that is where it is, but when I think of my memories, that house comes to mind. That wagon remains, but other people already live there” (Tahir, 2025).

For some, the word “home” evokes a flat, though others think of a house with a garden. It is instead a space with your loved ones for some, not just a physical structure. For others, it may mean an entire country. It may sometimes mean just a railway carriage. A longing just for all of the moments, for all of the days spent there, and for the childhood memories attached unite them. Even when he was a very young child, despite living in that house, he would talk about what the inside of the place he called home was like, what the rooms were like, and how they turned the carriage into a living room. Although his family briefly mentioned that they had lived in various places and difficult conditions, none of them had mentioned their life in the carriage. Since I was already informed, I did not ask his parents any further questions about this, but despite Tahir's family trying to raise their children in peace and without painful memories by talking only about good memories, some events are not erased from children's memories. When I spoke with families, I noticed that different members tended to talk about different topics. Some topics were left unsaid or toned down. As a researcher, I tried to listen carefully to each member's words and bring together different perspectives, considering these differences.

Tahir is hesitant about returning to Karabakh and rebuilding his life there. He said he could continue living there if the conditions, work environment, and salary were good, but he is hesitant to go due to the uncertainty about what work and life will be like in the current situation. The participant, who also stated that he was ready to provide all the support he could for his homeland, also stated that he really wanted to see those areas with his own eyes, at least visit them frequently. But one of the parts of the meeting that interested me was that he answered my question about living with Armenians positively, and even if his family did not accept him, he also expressed that he wanted them to choose to stay in peace rather than go and suffer as IDPs and continue their

lives. *“After all, I know very well what it means to be an IDP, and I do not want others, especially children, to experience this”.*

5.6. Burnt Village and Refugee Life – Mr. Rufat's Memories

After Tahir, who did not wish the life of an IDP on anyone, seeing the hardships of his own experiences, I had another meeting with Mr. Rufat²⁷ (pseudonym), the cousin of Tahir's father, Kamal Bey. Mr. Rufat (60 years old), who accepted to meet online from the city of Barda, where he currently lives as an IDP, recalls those days as follows:

“We left our village on March 12, 1993. A month before we left the village, the Armenians had burned the village. During that time, we were staying at my uncle's house. They were staying in another village. Because our house was burned down, we couldn't take anything from the house, we just ran away with our lives” (Rufat, 2025).

The family, unable to take anything from their home, at first settled in the Aghdam district. As the situation in Aghdam deteriorated further, after they had stayed briefly, they sought refuge in the district of Imishli. However, after a short period that they followed there, they returned once again to a village in Aghdam. After Aghdam's complete occupation, the family relocated to the Barda district. Since July 1993, they have lived in Barda as internally displaced persons. Their first shelter in Barda was within the Veterinary Department yard. It had been their very first place of shelter. Other displaced families filled the building when they arrived there. They therefore created for themselves a temporary living space in the yard.

“My childhood years until I was 27 were spent in that house. I remember everything, every place. It is impossible to forget. Leaving that house, not being able to take anything out of it, was hard not only for me, but for our entire family. At present, we have a house here, but it can never replace the one we left behind. That was the house where I grew up, and no other place can hold the same meaning for me. After the war, Armenians had settled in our house and completely changed its interior design. In February 2025, I had the opportunity to visit our former home. Although the structure still stands, it no longer feels like our home — it no longer carries our essence, nor the memories embedded in its walls. Even the trees in the yard were either cut down or left to wither. The yard was in poor condition, and restoration work has yet to begin in our village. There is no clear information about when resettlement will be possible, although from what I have seen, reconstruction

²⁷ Interview date: 16th of April 2025, Barda/Azerbaijan, online video call.

efforts are progressing rapidly. We were able to visit the area by registering through the state's official online portal and obtaining a permit. Now, we are eagerly waiting for the day we can finally return home.

War is a complicated subject for me. I myself was a war participant. I am a war veteran. We lost many martyrs in both wars. Some of my relatives were killed. The first Azerbaijani National Hero was my aunt's son. But it is not only this, I lost many martyrs from our close circle" (Rufat, 2025).

In response to the question of whether he could imagine living together with Armenians again, Mr. Rufat firmly answered, "*No, they killed my father in front of my eyes. We were together at war, it was March 3, 1992. My father was wounded in the war. We managed to take him to the hospital, but we couldn't save him.*" Interestingly, although Mr. Rufat did not mention his father while speaking about his losses earlier in the interview, his response to this specific question revealed that the memory of his father's death remains a harrowing and suppressed experience. His avoidance of recalling this event until prompted suggests the emotional difficulty of confronting certain memories and the lasting trauma associated with them.

Since such situations occurred during interviews, I sometimes had to repeatedly ask the same question to the participant in a different form, changing it. Although I sometimes didn't want to overdo it, considering the sensitivity of the topic, we occasionally discussed other issues to create a friendly environment where they could share their thoughts with me freely and without hesitation. But I think that sometimes people try to forget what happened in their minds to put it behind them or convince themselves that they did. It was not surprising for me to encounter this in such sensitive and difficult topics.

5.7. Aghdam and Unforgettable Memories

Following the occupation of Aghdara and the unforgettable memories it left behind, I now turn to the occupation of Aghdam, an event that gave rise to its painful recollections, carried by those who lived through it. It is with these memories and their owners that I move on to the next series of

encounters. I would like to share insights from my interview²⁸ with Tamara (pseudonym) Khanum (55 years old), a living witness to those events.

Both of Tamara Khanum's parents were born in different villages of the Aghdam district and settled together in Aghdam city after getting married. Tamara Khanum is one of four children (3 sisters and 1 brother) and was born and raised in Aghdam. She is currently living in Türkiye.

“Sometimes people forget the days that have passed, sometimes we forget what we did yesterday. But all those days, those memories that I lived until I left Aghdam, are all in my mind. When I close my eyes, they all come to mind...” (Tamara, 2024).

Tamara Khanum, who remembered every detail about her home and stated that she remembered the location of her belongings, even describing the trees in her yard, stated that she remembered where they were.

"Nothing has remained the same in Aghdam," she said, "but I feel as though I went there right now, I would find everything just as I left it." She described how vividly the roads, and the exact location of their house appeared in her memory, adding with teary eyes, *"I even managed to find the place where our house once stood using satellite images."* She went on to share that she remembers their house almost every single day. *"The day we were forced to leave Aghdam, everything, the roads, the streets, the way it all happened, plays before my eyes like a film reel, over and over again."*

The answer to the question of what war means to Tamara Khanum helps us to visualize what happened, at least a little:

“For me, war meant losing my childhood and my youth. It was so terrifying that it’s impossible to describe with words. Aghdam alone gave 6,500 martyrs. Among those martyrs was even my beloved (she said, swallowing hard to hold back her tears). One morning, you wake up and you must start your life from nothing, from zero. You live in peace, you have a house, and everything is within reach of you. I would even say you’re living in the most beautiful place in the world. But at 6 a.m., Grad missiles start to fall. That night, 17 of our young people were killed in a school building, and my beloved was among them. Right after that, they entered the city. They bombed the city. Houses were burning, and everyone was running. Back then, there were ZIL trucks²⁹. Around 50-60

²⁸ Interview date: 3rd of August 2024, Antalya/Türkiye, online video call.

²⁹ The ZIL-130 is a Soviet truck produced by ZIL in Moscow, Russia.

people would squeeze into them, trying to save their lives. And of course, we couldn't take anything from home - with just the clothes on our backs, we barely managed to escape with our lives. And then, as you know, displacement, refugee life, and all that. I don't even want to say that word. It sounds so offensive to me. As if they're insulting us, as if they're crushing us. And honestly, that's exactly what they were doing..."

Tamara Khanum's last words reminded me of Leyla Khanum's. Not accepting the word refugee was perhaps related to not accepting what they had experienced, the fact that they had lost their homes. After all, how could those who lived every day with the hope of returning accept that word?

From time to time, because the city was being shelled, people would gather in their cars and spend the night at a place called 'Four Roads' at the city's exit, then return to their homes in the morning. While they were standing there, the bodies of the martyrs arrived one by one. But the last time³⁰, even though everyone thought it would be the same again, after waiting for two days at Four Roads, when Tamara Khanum, her mother, and her uncle went back to their home to grab a few belongings, they saw that the entire city was already in flames, and the Armenian armed forces had entered the city. Realizing this, they barely managed to escape with their lives, running to avoid being taken captive.

Tamara Khanum mentioned that none of their immediate neighbors were taken captive, but people from the surrounding villages were. She recounted how even her aunt was once captured, but fortunately, the Armenian soldier who had taken her recognized her, as he was someone who used to regularly shop from her. Because of this, he let her go and allowed her to escape alone. Tamara Khanum also noted that this woman is still alive today.

She recalled how, during those times, the local people showed immense solidarity, supporting one another, opening their homes to those who had lost theirs. Tamara Khanum explained that after leaving their own house, they spent the night at an acquaintance's place. Yet, she remembered nothing from that night. Due to the overwhelming stress and grief, she couldn't sleep and, even now, she cannot recall any details of those hours. After staying at different acquaintances' houses for about a week, they eventually moved to Mingachevir city, where they were placed in a school building repurposed for displaced families. Tamara Khanum shared how they spent several years

³⁰ They left their homes 21st of June 1993, and wanted to return 23rd of June 1993 (the day when Aghdam was officially occupied), but they saw the city was on fire.

living there under harsh and difficult conditions. She recalled how, even to get bread, people had to queue for hours early in the morning. As she spoke of these memories, she seemed eager to move past them, babbling, as if hoping to leave those painful recollections behind.

Tamara Khanum shared:

"When I say 'homeland', what I mean is Aghdam. We have a WhatsApp group with my former classmates, and whenever we talk, they always repeat my words: 'Let's return to our homeland.' In fact, they are still in Azerbaijan, in their homeland, but I am not; I am far away from it. Yet for me, the homeland is Aghdam. In my dreams, it is always our house in Aghdam. There are many more beautiful houses now, but for me, it is only that one. For 30 years, I have longed for that house. Believe me, even now I still see it in my dreams.

I have been living in Türkiye for 18 years, and before that, I lived in Moscow. I am someone who dreams a lot, but whenever I see a house in my dreams, it's always our house in Aghdam. Even when my friends from Türkiye appear in my dreams, somehow, we are in my old house in Aghdam.

Back then, I was very fond of my clothes. Every time there was shelling in the city, I would run and gather my clothes, thinking, 'If something happens, who will collect them?' On the last day, we thought we would come back again, so we didn't take anything with us. But we never got the chance to return.

That's why I always see in my dreams that our house is still standing, but the Armenians have come to the door, and we are hurriedly gathering our belongings. I even remember clothes in my dreams that I had completely forgotten about in real life. Maybe to someone far away, this might sound strange or even amusing, but for me, it is deeply painful."

Tamara Khanum's words reveal how even the seemingly insignificant belongings can turn into deeply painful memories when they are lost. The most heartbreaking part is being forced to leave a place you loved without being able to take a single memento with you, watching your memories burn in front of your eyes. And from the ashes, all that remains are the moments you endlessly replay in your mind, just so you don't forget.

"My biggest wish is to return to Aghdam. I want to go back and live there. I would truly wish for everyone to be given back their own yard, their own house — but most probably, that won't happen. Since the city's structure has changed, different types of houses will be given. At the very least, I would want a house with a yard. The location doesn't matter; as long as it's in Aghdam, anywhere is fine. So far, we haven't been given any clear information about how the houses will be allocated. We submitted our house documents

and the old project plan, but there's still no definite news. The only thing we know is that there will mostly be apartment buildings in the city center." (Tamara, 2024).

Tamara Khanum mentioned that in Aghdam, everything was destroyed, even the trees were uprooted, and their roots were burned. She worked at a museum known as "Khan's Palace" and recalled that there were centuries-old plane trees in its courtyard. Sadly, even those ancient trees were uprooted and burned. She also shared that she managed to locate the spot where her house once stood by using satellite maps³¹, identifying the place from the fallen roots of broken plane trees nearby. That was how she could see the remnants of her home. The house marked in the picture is the one where the memories she spoke of took place. From the view (photo 3), it also becomes clear why Aghdam is often referred to as a "Ghost City". Although some villages and parts of the city center have seen reconstruction efforts since Aghdam was liberated from occupation³², the restoration process is still ongoing and has not yet been fully completed. Technological advances have radically transformed the experience of finding and returning to lost homes. People can now pinpoint the exact location of their homes, relive lost memories, and see a destroyed version of their homes without ever having to physically go there. This is a significant innovation in research, both methodologically and emotionally.

Tamara Khanum, who never accepted the idea of living in other cities of Azerbaijan, mentioned that she is counting down the hours to move back to Aghdam. She expressed her longing to live in Aghdam again, not in the new smart houses or modern city structures, but in the old Aghdam of her memories. She also mentioned that most of the people around her feel the same way; they don't wish for a smart city, but for the city they remember from the past. Currently, new technological and modern 'smart city' projects are being implemented in Aghdam. However, for the local population, this does not replace the simple and familiar landscape of the past. For them, the real Aghdam is the old city that keeps its memories alive. Information about the project is provided in the following sections.

³¹ After the liberation of the city of Aghdam from occupation, before the start of reconstruction works.

³² 20th of November 2020.

Photo 3: The remains of Tamara Khanim's houses in Aghdam city, which she found on a map. Source: Personal archive of Mrs. Tamara, August 2024.

I believe that the fear of not being able to find the Aghdam they remember, the one they hold in their memories, and the sadness of knowing the old houses and streets have been destroyed, creates a certain resistance to embracing the new. Still, I hope that once the reconstruction is completed and the people of Aghdam return to their lands, they will be able to reconnect with their memories. And though the city may look different, I hope that after this 30-year pause, they will find a way to continue the stories they left behind.

When speaking about Karabakh, about the memories of people filled with longing and hope, and while listening to their stories, one inevitably recalls sorrowful poems and traditional folk songs in their mind. As I listened to Tamara Khanum's memories, the melancholic strains of *Bayati-Shiraz*, often performed on remembrance days for Karabakh, echoed in my mind. Despite the pressures of the Soviet era, poet Mammad Araz³³ captured the pain of longing for the homeland in

³³ Mammad Araz was an Azerbaijani poet (1933-2004). His pen name, Araz, is the Azerbaijani spelling for the Aras River.

his verses, which later intertwined with the mournful melodies of *Bayati-Shiraz*, turning this piece into a cultural expression where those unable to put their sorrow into words found collective solace:

*You are a wingless heart that gave me wings,
I've burned for your ember, and called it "Homeland."
For every stone, every flower, every blade of grass you bear,
I've knelt down and called it "Homeland."*³⁴

To listen to the memories and thoughts of both the thousands of people who carry vivid recollections and haunting memories of Aghdam - the ghost city, in their minds, as well as the younger generation who grew up with these stories and imagined Aghdam in their dreams, I met with Ms. Gunash, a 26 July 1993-born descendant of an Aghdam family currently living in Hungary. It is important to note that Gunash is the niece of Tamara Khanum. We hold our conversation in a small café in Budapest, face to face on the 25th of July 2024.

Gunash, whose parents are from Shusha and Aghdam, left Aghdam with her mother when she was a newborn (2 months old). Gunash, who has been an IDP since birth, records her memories as follows:

“My mother and her family had to leave their home with nothing but identification documents and a few clothes. Initially, they relocated to the city of Ganja, staying with relatives for a short time before moving to Mingachevir. In Mingachevir, we first stayed with relatives for several days and were later settled into School No. 16. The state organized the accommodation for internally displaced persons, assigning each family a classroom to live in. My mother, grandmother, uncle, aunt, and I lived together in one classroom. We stayed in that school building until around 1998-1999, when I was about five or six years old” (Gunash, 2024).

Noting that they received aid from second-hand and hand-sewn clothing from UNESCO, Gunash recalls the years they spent living in school, waiting in lines for aid, the times when the school was flooded, and the difficulties of starting life as an internally displaced person. In 1998, while still living in the school building, Gunash lost her grandmother. She recalls that most of what she knows

³⁴ Azerbaijani Translation:

Mənə qanad verən odsuz ürəksən,
Yanıram közünə Vətən demişəm.
Hər daşın, hər çiçəyin, hər otun üçün,
Diz çöküb, gözünə Vətən demişəm.

about their home and life in Aghdam comes from the stories her grandmother used to tell. Her grandmother, who spent her final years as an internally displaced person, passed away holding on to the hope of one day returning to Aghdam. As Gunash spoke of her grandmother's longing for home and how her final days were marked by the unfulfilled dream of seeing her homeland again, her voice trembled. Listening to her, I felt as though I, too, had lived through those memories, as if I had personally sat in that cold classroom and longed for a home I had never seen.

Gunash, who learned about their home in Aghdam through the stories told by her family, spoke about how, in the early days of displacement, everyone believed they would soon return. She shared a poignant memory passed down to her: when her grandmother left their home for the last time, she didn't even tie up the chickens, saying, "*Let them roam and eat, we'll be back soon...*". This small, simple act reflects the enduring hope people carried with them, clinging to the belief of return until their final breath. Unfortunately, her grandmother was just one of those who waited with this hope but could not bear this longing for 30 years and lost her life as an IDP.

"Since I was in school and living in a rented house until I was 19, every place I stay is temporary for me. I can't say that the concept of home has been fully formed for me. Currently, I live abroad and I don't have a specific home. In many cities in Azerbaijan, and here, I don't have a home that I'm attached to. Since I have raised my family here and lived here, I can call this my home, but when it comes to my roots and homeland, I would say Aghdam" (Gunash, 2024).

Gunash, who did not think it would be possible to return to Aghdam after living in Budapest and adapt, but planned to go for a visit, notes that her mother, aunts, and uncle are eagerly waiting to return to Aghdam, but that there is currently no official information about the restoration of their homes, and they are waiting for their turn.

5.8. Mosques and Home: Parallel Icons in the System of Spiritual Values of Azerbaijanis

When Guneash and Tamara Khanum remember the Aghdam Mosque, they emphasize that these mosques are a symbol of the spiritual connection of religious beliefs and the home in Azerbaijani culture. Mosques, like homes, have both spiritual and cultural significance in people's lives. For people with religious beliefs, a mosque is considered a second home, and seeing its destruction among historical monuments seems to be the most important object in Azerbaijani culture. I would

say that trees and mosques are perhaps on the same level as the sensitivity people show to their homes. When talking about Agdam, it is impossible not to mention the Agdam Mosque, which witnessed all these tragedies.

I would like to state as a fact that the residents of Aghdam who shared their memories with me also mentioned that martyrs were collected not only from Aghdam, but also from other Karabakh territories and brought to the Aghdam Mosque. Even the bodies of the local civilians and children who were brutally murdered in the Khojaly genocide were first brought to the Aghdam Mosque and then handed over to their families. According to photos shared by the Embassy of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Islamic Republic of Iran, the Juma Mosque in Aghdam, also known as the Aghdam Mosque, was destroyed after the occupation and subsequently used as a stall for animals³⁵ (destroyed state photo 4.) (Embassy of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the Islamic Republic of Iran, 2016).

The Agdam Juma Mosque was also one of the main witnesses of the Khojaly tragedy. During the genocide, both martyrs and refugees from Khojaly were housed in the mosque. Those people stayed in the mosque for a while. Some of those brutally killed in Khojaly were frozen. Several martyrs even froze and fused. It was possible to separate them by washing them with hot water in the mosque (APA Information Agency, 2022).

The Aghdam Mosque was one of the first historical monuments to be restored after the war, and its restoration work is now fully completed. Although the mosque was subjected to insults and destruction for many years under occupation, it has not lost its historical and spiritual significance for the local population and the state (as a cultural heritage). The restoration of the Aghdam Mosque is also considered a restoration of the historical memory, religious and cultural values of

³⁵ For more detailed info and photos the website of the embassy: <https://tehran.mfa.gov.az/>

the Azerbaijani people. Currently, the mosque, in addition to restoring its former appearance, has become a symbol of peace and return in the region, although it carries bitter memories.

Photo 4: Aghdam Juma Mosque under the occupation. Source: Tehran.mfa.gov.az

5.9. The New Definition of Home: Relationships, Not Geographical Space

After Aghdam, one of the cities occupied was Jabrayil³⁶. I would also like to include the reflections of Nijat, a representative of the younger generation born after the war (February 1, 1999), who has roots in Jabrayil. An in-person meeting was held with Nijat on August 4, 2024, in Budapest, where we discussed his thoughts and memories related to Jabrayil.

³⁶ Occupation date: 23.08.1993.

His parents were residents of Chullu village in Jabrayil district. Many people in that village were related to each other. Those lost happy memories spent together were memories that Nijat, a new member of the family, listened to from his childhood. In July 2024, the family, who returned to their land for the first time to visit³⁷, noted that they encountered only the destroyed walls of the house and that the house, including the trees in the yard, was in a dilapidated and unusable state.

“For me, home is not a specific house or place — it is the environment where I am surrounded by my loved ones. I do not feel attached to a particular physical space. Wherever my loved ones are, that is home for me. I prefer not to burden the concept of 'home' with a fixed identity. As long as the place I live in is safe, it becomes home. Currently, I live in Budapest, and if I were to move to another country, I wouldn't necessarily miss my home here, but I might miss the people around me. While my parents would like to return and settle in Jabrayil, I do not have such a plan. At present, roads have been reconstructed in Jabrayil, but residential areas have not yet been fully restored” (Nijat,2024).

Nijat, whose parents registered in Baku and voluntarily left the status of IDP, because they owned a house, but still, he has the status of IDP because he is registered in the Jabrayil district's municipality. New family members born while his parents were registered in the occupied regions were also registered in that region. For example, Nijat, although born in 1999, is registered as a resident of the Jabrayil region, which was occupied in 1993. The subsequent deregistration of his family did not prevent him from remaining in this registration.

“My parents got married in June 1993, and in August of the same year, the city was occupied. Afterward, while my mother and her family settled in the city of Sheki, my father returned to Aghdam and served as a soldier for seven years in the frontline areas of the villages that remained under Azerbaijani control. He worked as a commander during this period. We (he and his sister) were born and raised in a rented house in the village of Chamanli, near the frontline. During those years, the ceasefire was occasionally violated by Armenian forces. On one such occasion, when I was a child, my father was wounded in an attack” (Nijat, 2024).

I think this story clearly shows the profound impact of war on families and the hardships experienced by those serving on the front lines. The life experiences of people like Nijat's father,

³⁷ Date of liberation from occupation: 4th of October 2020 (the first liberated territory).

who fought on the front lines, highlight how war is remembered in the memories of family members not only for its physical devastation, but also for its moral and emotional impact.

5.10. State Support and the Future of Karabakh: The Role of the State

This section examines the state's vision for the future of Karabakh, including the creation of spaces that are considered temporary homes. The focus is on the state's support for internally displaced persons after the war, social programs, and reconstruction policies.

During the interviews, it became clear that some middle-aged participants censored their responses on critical issues regarding the state. This section briefly reviews the types of support provided to IDPs, as well as participants' differing opinions on whether the support is sufficient. The social benefits and financial assistance offered are briefly presented, based on official data from the State Committee.

According to interviews, IDPs are exempt from electricity, gas, and water costs up to a certain limit. Young people receive education at the state's expense, and families receive monthly financial assistance of 50-60 AZN³⁸, which is enough only to buy bread.

According to the State Committee for Refugees and IDPs, IDPs receive a monthly allowance of 33 or 60 AZN. In 2019, this amount increased by 50%. The allowance is not provided to administrative officials, entrepreneurs, those married to someone without status, those living abroad for a long time, or military personnel.

The 2004 program stopped the eviction of IDPs from their previous places of residence. Education fees are paid by the state, schoolchildren are given free textbooks, priority is given in workplaces, and medical services and medicines are free. IDPs are exempt from court, tax, and notary fees (The State Committee for Refugees and IDPs, 2019).

³⁸ Azerbaijani Currency – manat (AZN). 1 AZN is 2,12 PLN (3rd of July 2025).

6. THE FINAL REFLECTIONS ON HOME AND RETURNING

For the latest information shared about those who are eagerly waiting to move back to their homes and internally displaced persons who are joyfully reunited with their renovated homes, I would like to briefly summarize the speech of Fuad Huseynov, Deputy Chairman of the State Committee for Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons, on the topic of “Solution of the Internally Displaced Persons Problem in Azerbaijan and the Great Return” to 31 diplomats from 27 countries within the framework of the “The Advanced Foreign Service Program” for foreign diplomats held in collaboration with ADA University, operating under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The speech noted that the “Great Return” process is one of the main goals in the “Azerbaijan 2030” National Priorities. Currently, extensive infrastructure projects are being implemented in the territories. The State Committee and ADA University are jointly organizing sociological surveys, educational events, and hotline services among the displaced. Armenia’s contamination of the territories with mines was noted as one of the main obstacles to the return process. In particular, the failure to share maps of mined areas for the demining of the Aghdam and Aghdara regions is further slowing down the clearance procedures (The State Committee for Refugees and IDPs, 2025).

Construction work is underway in the liberated territories, and the process of returning former internally displaced persons to their native lands continues within the framework of the “Great Return” program. During the 11 months of 2023, 901 families (3,516 people), and by the end of December, 987 families (3,932 people) returned to their native lands. By January 30, 2024, 1,360 families (5,354 people) had already settled in their native lands. According to the state program, it is planned to return 34,500 families, that is, approximately 140 thousand internally displaced persons, to their native lands by the end of 2026. For this purpose, modern residential areas, social infrastructure, schools, hospitals, and road and transport projects are being implemented in the region (New Azerbaijan Party, 2024).

Speaking of returning, I would like to mention Smart Homes as a project that was created. Smart project is a modern approach that aims to improve the quality of life of people, strengthen the

economy, and protect the environment by using digital technologies, cloud solutions, artificial intelligence, sensor systems, and innovative services in the management of cities and villages. Within the framework of this project, areas such as energy consumption, water supply, waste management, transport, security, and social services are automated and managed more effectively with smart technologies. For the first time, "Smart city" and "Smart village" projects are being implemented in Karabakh and East Zangazur regions. These projects are considered the most advanced technological projects not only in Azerbaijan, but also in the South Caucasus and the region.

Shusha city has been selected as a pilot smart city within the framework of the Smart City project. Smart lighting, smart transport systems, digital tourism services (mobile applications, robot guides), smart security cameras, cloud technology management, and environmental monitoring are planned here. At the same time, a green energy zone is being created, and renewable energy sources will be used. Smart solutions will be implemented for tourism and passenger flow that reduce environmental impact.

Within the framework of the Smart Village project, the first Smart Village project was successfully implemented in the village of Aghaly (Zangilan district). Smart irrigation systems, smart waste management, sensor water meters, electricity consumption control systems, electronic agricultural platforms, and digital community services were established here. The digitalization of agriculture, entrepreneurship, and social services is envisaged. Support will also be created for startup and social innovation projects. As a result, the Smart City and Smart Village projects implemented in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan will shape Karabakh as both an ecologically clean and technologically advanced region, as well as a regional Technopark and innovation center. Thanks to these projects, the Karabakh region will become a tourist destination, a startup factory, a green energy zone, and a technological innovation center (Guliyeva, 2021).

Sabuhi Abdullayev, Deputy Chairman of the Rehabilitation, Construction and Management Service for Aghdam, Fuzuli and Khojavand regions, said that the "Smart Village" project will be implemented in Bash Garvend village, one of the largest villages in the Aghdam region. Within the framework of the project, "smart solutions" will be applied by specialists and engineers from Slovakia. The village will be completely rebuilt on a total area of 476 hectares of Bash Garvend village and restored as a "smart village". In the first stage, 851 individual residential houses are

planned to be built on an area of 275 hectares. Within the framework of the project, a green energy production facility will be built for waste disposal and wastewater treatment. In addition to the use of natural materials in house construction, the application of smart technologies is also envisaged. In the future, it is planned to create solar heat pumps, charging stations for electric cars, solar collector systems, parking lots equipped with solar panels, and other smart technologies in the area (NEWS.AZ, 2024).

In Aghdam, a city where no stone has been left standing, the idea of smart homes may seem strange, but it offers a glimmer of hope for the revival and restoration of life in a long-abandoned homeland. However, it should be noted that many of the returnees are not so enthusiastic about the idea of smart homes, preferring more traditional and familiar spaces, longing to see their own homes, their own yards, when they return.

6.1. Karabakh University: Education and Hope for the Future

As one of the projects that brought Karabakh to life, I believe that Karabakh University plays a crucial role in the project of return and revival.

Karabakh University was established on November 28, 2023. The university, located in the city of Khankendi, operates as a public legal entity under the Ministry of Science and Education. Starting September 23, 2024, Karabakh University began its first academic year with 1154 students, 6 faculties, and 27 programs. The main building houses five faculties - Education, Engineering, Economics, Tourism, and Humanities and Social Sciences - offering 22 undergraduate programs. The university has apartment-style dormitories for students.

It should be noted that Karabakh University operates in the building of the Azerbaijan Pedagogical Institute, which was established in the city of Khankendi in 1969 (Karabakh University, 2024).

Unlike the return of people who left their homes in Karabakh, the departure of young people from Karabakh to study at a newly opened university raises the question of how they will adapt to the new city. In order to get the thoughts of the participants I interviewed in this direction, I presented this question to them during the meeting with Gunash.

“I believe this is a very positive step. It will bring fresh energy and vitality to the city. The fact that young people will be the first to move there will help revitalize the city” (Gunash, 2024).

I would agree with Gunash's words. But how is the adaptation of young people going? How will the academic staff who start working there adapt to a new environment far from their homes? In this regard, I had an online meeting with Dr. A³⁹., a member of the academic staff of Karabakh University.

“The establishment of Karabakh University was wonderful news for all of us, especially the fact that such a university was opened in Khankendi. From the very first days of its foundation, I expressed my willingness to support the university voluntarily in any capacity related to higher education and teaching, should there be a need. Eventually, a vacancy was announced, and I applied. Without any change in my position, I transferred from my role at Azerbaijan State University of Economics to Karabakh University” (Dr. A., 2024).

Dr. A., who spoke about the selection process at Karabakh University and his personal motivation for joining, is originally not from the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan. Although he is not a native of Karabakh, he expressed his willingness to voluntarily contribute to any educational initiatives wherever needed in the country. Smiling, he remarked: “*I’ve been connected with Karabakhis for 10 years now; my children are half Karabakhi, but that didn’t influence my decision.*” His words reflect how citizens without direct ties to Karabakh also feel motivated and mobilized to help give a new breath and life into the region.

As a student, having experienced that motivation is the most important factor in adapting to a new place by living in other cities and countries, I could understand the impact of this well.

Dr. A., who has been residing in the city of Khankendi since August 1, 2024, mentioned that although he initially traveled to Baku every 7 to 10 days, he has recently adapted to life in Karabakh and has not visited Baku for the past month. He attributed this both to an increased workload and his quick adjustment to the city’s lifestyle. “*My family lives in Baku. Every time I talk to my children, they ask, "When are you coming?" There are also difficult aspects of living here. But these never tire me. I have motivation, I have enthusiasm.*” He emphasized that the living conditions are of a high standard and that residents, including university staff, have been

³⁹ Interview date: 29th of November 2024. Online videocall from Khankendi, Karabakh University. By agreement, an abbreviation of the surname was used.

comfortably accommodated. *“If I’m not mistaken, the city of Khankendi covers an area of 170 hectares, and the Karabakh University campus alone occupies 70 hectares. It is set to become the largest university in Azerbaijan in the near future. The residential apartments provided for us are also conveniently located near the university campus,”* he noted.

Describing his home merely as a place to sleep, Dr. A. explained that due to his heavy workload, he spends most of his day at the office and prefers to eat and socialize in various spots around the city, leaving little time to be at home. For this reason, he noted that his house carries no particular emotional meaning for him. Reflecting on his current accommodation, he recalled that when he first moved in, the absence of a work desk and his request for a piano were quickly addressed, yet *“I haven’t even played a single note on the piano for 10 minutes. And that tells me that the house, for now, is simply a place to sleep,”* he admitted sincerely.

Dr. A. associated this sense of detachment with having left his family at the age of 15 to pursue his studies, spending years living in different dormitories and rented apartments. *“But I do have one dream,”* he added. *“I dream of designing my own house — a home where I can settle down when I grow older. I’ve already bought the land for it, next to the land where my father was born. Maybe once I build that house and start living there, that feeling of belonging will finally come to me.”*

In fact, these words also imply that for people to feel a sense of belonging, there must be a value that connects them to that place. For some, this value is childhood memories, joyful moments, a yard that witnessed their growth, or the footprints of their ancestors. The sense of belonging that is thought to arise in this meeting also comes from somewhere, from the land that stands for ancestors, which has meaning.

While discussing the accommodation and adaptation processes of students at Karabakh University, based on Dr. A.'s remarks, it became clear that the university was envisioned not only as an educational institution for the people of Karabakh but also for other Azerbaijanis from across the country. He emphasized that students have been provided with high-standard dormitories and that the university’s construction and development processes are progressing at an impressive pace.

Referring to the institution, which had celebrated its first anniversary just a day before our interview, Dr. A. remarked: *“They didn’t let us crawl — we had to start running from the very*

beginning.” From his responses, it was also evident that the motivation and collective efforts of other staff members have significantly contributed to this rapid progress.

Dr. A. sincerely emphasized that the quality of education at Karabakh University is currently at a level that, in his words, *"cannot be compared to other universities in Azerbaijan."* He also highlighted the importance of the social opportunities created for students alongside academic education. According to him, various projects are being implemented to improve both the students' hard skills and soft skills. *"More important than the education itself is what additional knowledge and skills they acquire during their studies. We are actively working on this. Our aim is that, by the time they graduate after four years, not only will they receive a diploma, but at least 35–40% of our students will also have obtained internationally recognized certificates."*

Speaking about the connections and systems established by the university, Dr. A. briefly touched upon the environment created for students:

"From what we observe, the students seem happy. Most of them are 17 years old. The city is quite interesting. Everyone greets each other in the streets, students play football with the police officers, and there is a sincere atmosphere. The police care about the students, and everyone pays attention to them. We are not only establishing a university here; the city itself is forming around it in a warm, welcoming way" (Dr. A., 2024).

He further noted that teachers and students often go to the gym together and engage in informal conversations. From these remarks, it becomes evident that conscious efforts are being made to help students adapt and feel comfortable in their new environment.

“After signing the peace agreement, if Armenians no longer make territorial claims against Azerbaijan and avoid any terrorist or separatist activities, we have no issues with anyone. In the future, if an Armenian citizen expresses a desire to study at Karabakh University in Khankendi, they are welcome to do so. The mindset here is extremely important. There is absolutely no aggression from our side. Even the building we are currently using was originally constructed by the Azerbaijani government in 1969. If they accept these realities and wish to live and study here, they are completely free to do so. When we open our university to international students in the future, they will also be able to come and pursue their education here as international students. There are Armenians who currently remain here in Khankendi; neither our people nor our students have anything against them. Our nation is humane; we have no racism, no chauvinism, and no use of force against helpless and powerless individuals” (Dr. A., 2024).

At present, Khankendi is one of the cities where some Armenians continue to reside voluntarily. In this context, as both a member of the academic staff and a resident of the same city, Dr. A.'s perspectives were particularly meaningful for me. Having previously been one of my lecturers during my education in Azerbaijan, Dr. A.'s views now play an important role in shaping the opinions of students at Karabakh University. His positive and inclusive response not only pleased me personally but also gave me hope that peaceful coexistence might be possible in the future.

7. CONCLUSION

This dissertation analyzes the concepts of home, place, and identity through the eyes of IDPs returning to Karabakh, revealing that the process of return carries not only geographical but also deep social, psychological, and emotional meaning. The data obtained during the research showed that for IDPs, the concept of "home" is not just a building or a piece of land but is rich in symbolic meanings that it carries with childhood memories, family relationships, lost friends, and a past way of life. The process of returning to Karabakh takes place against the backdrop of both a change in the physical environment and the conflict between individual and collective memory.

As a result of the interviews, it became clear that in addition to the desire of the majority of respondents to return to the lands of their birth, some participants also carry a sense of nostalgia and regret that their homes will no longer be the same when they return, as they are still waiting. While for some, returning means a new beginning and the opportunity to relive unfinished memories, for others, it means facing the loss of their old lifestyle and environment. The information obtained showed that the concept of "home" among IDPs is not only a physical space, but also a feeling and value preserved in memory. At the same time, during the interviews, I expected that although young people were born into IDP families and expressed their thoughts, feelings, and the difficulties of growing up in a more relaxed and free manner, the group that witnessed the war and spent their youth under the influence of the Soviet Union carefully chose their words and expressed their thoughts and difficulties, fearing to speak out against the state. I think this stems from the way they were raised and the political censorship of freedom of speech since childhood (during the Soviet era). At the same time, unlike the older generation, young people do not seem to be very willing to leave the cities where they grew up and built their lives and return to Karabakh permanently at the current stage.

It is very difficult for me to generalize the interviews conducted. Because, as can be seen from the memories shared by people during the interviews, even though every family shared the same fate, they tried to hold on to life again through different paths and challenges. The material and moral losses were different for everyone, and everyone lived in not-so-glorious moments and places while trying to find a home and a place of safety. It is also very difficult to generalize both the

historical hardships and the current experiences. Because the feelings of internally displaced persons who have returned to their homes in a condition close to their former state (as we saw in the case of Lachin city) and those whose homes were completely destroyed, burned, and whose future is uncertain, waiting in a state of anticipation (as we saw in the case of Aghdam city), are at completely different stages.

At the same time, considering that everyone who reads these interviews will internalize the participants' feelings and words in different ways, I preferred to avoid generalizing their thoughts in my own words and instead chose to keep them in their original form as much as possible, as quotations.

This study also confirmed that the Karabakh conflict and long-term displacement are among the main factors that profoundly shape collective memory and national identity in Azerbaijani society. The process of return means the reconstruction of memory and a sense of identity at both the individual and societal levels. At the same time, ethnographic observations and interviews showed that the newly built smart villages and cities bring new challenges to the adaptation process of internally displaced persons, both socially and culturally.

The results I obtained from the interviews show that people returning to Karabakh return not only to their homeland and homes, but also to their past, to their lost and incomplete memories. As Thomas Wolfe noted in his work *You Can't Go Home Again* (Wolfe, 1934), returning to one's homeland is not only a physical act, but also an encounter with oneself, one's past, one's moments, one's emotional ties, and memories. For some interviewees returning to Karabakh, this return, along with joy and nostalgia, also evokes feelings of anxiety and alienation to a certain extent. Because the place they knew as their homeland has changed, and new smart home projects have been created in place of their old houses that were destroyed. This confirms, as Wolfe emphasizes, that the concept of "home" is a constantly changing phenomenon that does not always remain in the past. As a result, this study shows that the process of returning to Karabakh is a complex and contradictory experience on both the physical, social, and psychological levels. This can be explained by comparing it with Wolfe's approach. It is inevitable that there will be people whose expectations will not be met.

In this sense, the return to Karabakh illustrates how places are never fixed but are emotionally and socially constructed spaces that change along with people's memories and expectations.

By documenting the experiences of returnees, this study adds an ethnographically grounded perspective to broader anthropological discussions on post-conflict return, the politics of memory, and the emotional geographies of displacement.

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ATTACHMENTS

Interview Questions

1. How would you describe your personal connection to the Karabakh region?
2. Where were you born and raised?
3. What does 'home' mean to you?
4. Do you feel attached to a particular home or place?
5. How did you have to leave your home? What circumstances forced you to do so?
6. What was said about your home and the region before the occupation? How was it remembered or described at that time?
7. What does 'war' mean to you? How did it affect your life and the lives of those around you?
8. Would you like to return to Karabakh?
9. How was the state support for IDPs after displacement, and how would you describe the current situation?
10. How do you perceive the development of the newly liberated territories today?
11. In your opinion, what is the most important factor for the sustainable development of these areas? (For example: infrastructure, employment opportunities, restoration of cultural heritage, rebuilding social relations, etc.)
12. What are your thoughts on elderly people's adaptation to smart homes and smart cities?
13. What do you think about the prospect of both Azerbaijani and Armenian communities living together again in Karabakh? Under what conditions could this be possible?